

DIGITAL SOVEREIGNTY IN THE ENERGY SECTOR

ENFORCEMENT AND MONITORING OF
DATA SOVEREIGNTY POLICIES
(EMDAS)

TASK 1.1 - UNIVERSITY OF TRENTO

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1. Abstract of the Deliverable

Digital sovereignty has become the loadstar of EU innovation policies. But it does not have a widely agreed meaning. This report, drafted for the EMDAS project, explores this apparent paradox with regard to the twin transition in the energy sector. The main argument is that the multiple meanings of digital sovereignty allow the EU and the Member States to implement regulatory measures that shape their industrial policies. A distinction between the collective and the individual dimension of digital sovereignty is proposed to analyse the contents of such regulatory choices in two domains: cybersecurity and data protection. Reference is made to both EU horizontal legislation and to legislation in the energy sector. Italian legislation is analysed to assess how sovereignty concerns are taken up at Member State level. The report concludes with four policy recommendations, related to the joint assessment of the collective and individual dimensions, the geopolitical relevance of sustainability standards, the mechanisms to control supply chains, and the conflicting sovereignty claims in the energy sector.

2. Introduction: the regulatory side of digital sovereignty

‘Digital autonomy is no longer a luxury – it is the foundation of sovereignty’ (Bria et al. 2025, 13). This dramatic statement opens the report in which a consortium of European research centres depicts the challenges the EU has to address to shape its own version of the digital economy. According to this view, it is not just a matter of technological innovation and economic competitiveness. Democracy and fundamental rights are at stake. Much the same perspective had already emerged a few months earlier with the appointment, in the second von der Leyen Commission, of a vice-president for Tech Sovereignty, Security and Democracy.

The problem is that digital sovereignty has no agreed meaning. It might be related to the geopolitical tensions of the early twenty-first century. Or to the loss of competitiveness of the EU. It might even be argued that its uncertain meaning is not a bug, but a feature: diverging interests can use it to build coalitions (Wenzelburger and König 2025). Each scientific discipline could use it to focus on different aspects. No less relevant, the EU concept of digital sovereignty could not be compatible with similar concepts developed outside the EU. Though, some questions need to be answered: can digital sovereignty be used to build coherent regulatory frameworks? Does it allow to select specific regulatory options and discard other ones? Do those options foster EU’s autonomy? Do they also foster the autonomy of all EU citizens?

This report explores the possibility that, when deployed in the energy sector, the concept of digital sovereignty might explain specific regulatory choices in the EU.* For several reasons, such a perspective might prove useful.

To begin with, the concept of ‘strategic energy autonomy’ is widely referred to by EU institutions (e.g. EC 2023b, d) and can be said to be a counterpart to the concept of digital sovereignty. For a long time, the energy sector has been struggling with a variety of security concerns. The most traditional one related to country and EU dependency from external suppliers of fossil fuels. The low-carbon transition introduced new concerns, mostly related to the availability of raw materials and the control of supply chains for clean technologies (Jerzyński and Herranz-Surallés 2024). These energy dependencies amplify the perception of geopolitical and competitiveness risks usually highlighted by the concept of digital sovereignty. It doesn’t help that the EU has explicitly linked the low-carbon and the digital transitions. While synergies from both processes are potentially huge, each of them could be stymied by the failure to address sovereignty concerns. The ongoing digitalization of the energy sector transforms the relationships along the energy supply chains. Clearly, such transformations cannot be pursued in ways that increase EU dependencies from foreign states or business parties.

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At the same time, a regulatory strategy aimed at erasing any dependency is not credible. There are too many of them, and they can also be beneficial. The real goal is the transformation of those dependencies. It is at this point, however, that disagreements become visible. The direction and pace of such transformation are highly contentious. Moreover, the transformation impacts countries, companies and people outside the EU. If digital sovereignty is to provide a sound guide for regulatory interventions, the trade-offs it entails have to be laid bare.

Section 3 presents the methodology for the analysis of the concept of digital sovereignty in the energy sector. A distinction is drawn between collective and individual dimensions of sovereignty. Section 4 describes the digitalization process in the energy sector and how such process could interact with the two dimensions of the sovereignty discourse. Section 5 shows that, in the EU regulatory regime for cybersecurity, the collective dimension prevails. Section 6 shows that, in the EU data governance regime, the collective and individual dimensions coexist and can also clash. For both regulatory domains, the implementation of EU measures in the Italian legal system is assessed. Section 7 proposes policy recommendations to reduce the tensions between the collective and individual dimensions of sovereignty in the energy sector.

3. Methodology

Two key methodological choices are made. First, the extremes of techno-solutionism and legal solutionism are rejected. The former identifies those approaches that aim at exploiting the revolutionary potential of technologies to deeply change social relations. As pointed out by Sætra and Selinger (2024), it becomes a misguided approach when it forgets to consider the plurality of value systems and visions of the good life. Legal solutionism is associated with the idea that any technological risks can be managed with appropriate legal interventions. It omits to consider the multiple ways in which legal rules can fall short of a reasonable degree of control on such risks. At a more abstract level, the two extremes reflect the alternative between ‘code is law’ and ‘law is code’. Both approaches can be misguided to the extent the regulation of behaviour is never exclusively shaped by technologies or rules. The methodological perspective argued for here starts from the premise that technological innovation is embedded in wider social, economic, political and institutional contexts. The concept of digital sovereignty is influenced by those contexts and can shape the content and pace of innovation.

Moving from this premise, the second methodological choice is to draw on several disciplines to identify the possible roles of digital sovereignty. Each discipline sheds light on relevant factors, but concepts, methods and objectives are different. For example, political science studies deal with the legitimacy of EU policies aimed at shaping the direction of technological investments and with the forging of new coalitions supporting or hampering green industrial policies. Economic studies analyse the efficiency and incentive-compatibility of policies inspired by sovereignty concerns. Legal studies discuss the institutional underpinnings of digital sovereignty and the legal bases for the new EU industrial policy. Integrating all the contributions in a coherent theoretical framework goes beyond the goals of this report. What can be attempted here is an interdisciplinary approach that selects relevant factors highlighted from different disciplines and explores their connections. The question to be answered is whether sovereignty concerns lead to prioritize specific regulatory options and discard or downplay different ones.

The connections among the relevant factors are made visible through the distinction between the collective and the individual dimensions of digital sovereignty. The former justifies regulatory interventions aimed at reducing digital dependencies of the EU as a whole. The latter justifies regulatory interventions aimed at fostering spaces of individual self-determination. The distinction resonates with political science approaches that underline the need to understand for whom digital sovereignty has to be won and what is the scope of envisaged beneficiaries (Mügge 2024). The distinction also reflects the stated goal of a human-centred digital transformation, explicitly endorsed with the European Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles for the Digital Decade (EC 2022a). At least in theory, the two dimensions can interact. If digital sovereignty works to the benefit of the EU as a whole, EU citizens should benefit as well. Still, the distinction is useful because the

collective dimension might not generate benefits for all citizens and might even conflict with the individual dimension. In sec. 3, each dimension of sovereignty is associated with four distinct regulatory choices.

In line with the EMDAS project, the areas of cybersecurity and data protection are singled out to assess whether and when the concept of digital sovereignty is really able to steer the EU decision-making process. For both areas, the analysis includes the horizontal regulatory regimes and the energy regulatory regimes. The Italian implementation of EU legislation is used to check the congruence between the regulatory approaches at EU and Member State level.

4. Digitalization and sovereignty in the EU energy sector

In this section, we begin by describing how the EU linked its digitalization strategies to the low-carbon transition (sec. 4.1), then turn to the relevance of the collective and individual dimensions for sovereignty discourses (sec. 4.2).

4.1 The twin transition: synergies and new dependencies

In the energy sector, digital technologies can be deployed for several purposes. Since the 2000s, the cluster of technologies related to smart grids was promoted to improve network management. Later on, digital technologies helped integrate increasing shares of renewable energy, support the spread of decentralized energy resources, implement energy efficiency policies, and connect different energy infrastructures, as well as the energy sector and other sectors of the economy (buildings, mobility and industry). At the most general level, the digitalization of the energy sector entails three transformations (Montero and Finger 2021): first, data-producing devices allow to collect a much larger amount of information about infrastructures, energy producers and energy users; second, data are transmitted and made available to a larger number of users; third, data processing becomes increasingly sophisticated and automated, thus enhancing the opportunities for new energy services. Each of these three digital transformations was affected by consecutive waves of technological innovations in the ITC sector. Though, none of them can be understood as a simple technology transfer from the ICT sector to the electricity sector. Which digital innovations are supported, how they are supported and what their impact is depends on several regulatory choices. The most significant one is how the interplay between digitalization strategies and decarbonization strategies should be understood.

The EU has been more outspoken than the USA in linking the low-carbon and the digital transitions. In the European Green Deal communication (EC 2019b: 7), the digital transformation was identified as ‘a key enabler for reaching the Green Deal objectives’. Much emphasis on the twin ecological and digital transitions was also put in the Digital Europe communication (EC 2020b) and in the Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030 (Dec. 2022/2481).

With the eruption of the pandemic crisis and the Russia-Ukraine crisis, the twin transition became the main axes of the EU recovery plans. About two thirds of the total expenditures planned by Member States were bound to objectives in these two areas, thus largely exceeding the minimum targets set by Reg. 2021/241.

The New Industrial Strategy (EC 2020c) and the Green Deal Industrial Plan for the Net-Zero Age (EC 2023a) both suggested that the competitiveness and strategic independence of the EU were directly related to the quality and quantity of the resources devoted to the twin transition.

The action plan for digitalizing energy (EC 2022d) represented the most sustained attempt at putting in place the coordination mechanisms which could foster the synergies while at the same time controlling for the collateral impacts of the two transitions. It proposed initiatives in three areas: using digital tools to increase energy affordability, exploiting the greening potential of ICT, and strengthening the resilience of the energy sector.

Its scope is going to be further extended with the Strategic Roadmap for Digitalisation and Artificial Intelligence (AI) for the Energy Sector, to be adopted in 2026 (EC 2025b, g). It should accelerate the rollout of European AI solutions in areas such as electricity grid optimisation, energy efficiency in buildings and industry, and demand-side flexibility. Additionally, the Roadmap will foster AI-driven research and innovation by connecting start-ups with energy companies while ensuring robust safeguards for cybersecurity, data privacy and safety.

Member States were explicitly asked to promote an integrated approach to the twin transition in their National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs) (EC 2022e, 33) and in the REPowerEU chapters of the Recovery and Resilience Plans (EC 2022b, 25f.).

Digital and energy investment priorities also became the reference points in the external relationships with the main commercial partners (EC 2021, 2022c). The EU strategy is aligned with the views of international organizations on the close relationship between digitalization and decarbonization (IEA 2017, 2023).

Whether twinning really happens and what its impact on decarbonization is hinges on several factors. The distinction between modular and architectural innovation is useful here (Geels and Turnheim 2024, 31-33). Digitalization can amount to no more than modular substitution. For example, new sensors and communications devices are added on top of the physical grid, but they do not significantly change the relationships between network operators and users. Or digitalization can prompt architectural reshaping, with a complete overhaul of technological complementarities and innovative solutions. Whether incremental or radical innovations prevail is not only a matter of technological choices. The strategies pursued by innovators and incumbents matter as well (Mäkitie et al. 2023, 4).

Furthermore, the dynamics of the digital and the energy sectors may significantly diverge. Innovation in the ICT sector is usually faster, but it does not automatically translate into an accelerated transition for the energy sector. The latter is much more dependent on infrastructures which adapt to radically new technologies with a significant time lag (Fouquet and Hippe 2022). Other factors could reduce or slow down twinning opportunities. There is significant uncertainty about the real environmental benefits of digital technologies. Twinning should mean that the ICT sector is sustainable in itself and, at the same time, contributes to the decarbonization goals (Mäkitie et al., 2023: 4). Both conditions cannot be fulfilled without focused interventions.

There is, however, a broader issue that twinning strategies cannot escape. Digital markets have a strong tendency toward oligopolistic equilibria. A few tech giants, mostly from the USA and China, were able to control innovation processes and build up intellectual monopolies which leave no room for new entrants (Rikap and Lundvall 2021). Already in the 2010s, these developments sparked the debate about EU digital sovereignty. France, Germany and Spain were the most vocal proponents of industrial and innovation policies that could preserve EU countries' technological leadership. They succeeded in prompting the European Commission to build EU digital strategies onto the sovereignty perspective (Roch and Oleart 2024). Though, such a perspective makes it more difficult to devise digitalization strategies for the energy sector.

On one hand, energy companies are wary of transferring control of their infrastructures and their customer base to digital companies, be they from the EU or not. As observed by Niet and van Est (2025, 31), 'Big Tech companies can largely determine what the electricity and IT ecosystems look like and when and how they are used'. On the other hand, to the extent they choose to digitalize their business, energy companies have to comply with the restrictions imposed to non-EU providers of technologies.

How serious is the EU digital dependency? Using data for the 2010-2019 period, Mayer and Lu (2025) develop a Digital Dependency Index to measure the degree of dependence of 23 countries from foreign ICT (hardware, platforms, and patents). The USA and China are the only 'techopoles' with a high degree of autonomy and the capacity to yield their infrastructural power against other countries. In the 2010-2019 period, the autonomy gap between the least dependent state (the USA) and other countries has widened by an average of 11%. For the second least dependent state (China), the gap widened even more, by an average of 14%. This means that the USA and China reduced their digital dependence relative to other advanced economies. Also, China was

able to narrow its autonomy gap with the USA. Italy has a higher level of digital dependence than Germany and France, particularly with regard to the platform and patent dimensions. This analysis does not consider other crucial digital infrastructures, for example satellites, cloud services and digital payments. However, it clearly shows the bipolar structure of the global digital economy. It also shows that neither the USA nor China control all digital technologies. Dependent countries enjoy room for strategic manoeuvring between the two dominant technopoles, but they also face constraints related to their trade relationships and security concerns (Lehdonvirta et al. 2025).

Data from the European Commission confirmed that, by mid-2020s, several dependencies had to be coped with. According to the External Vulnerability Index (Garcia and Ho 2025), the EU is more vulnerable to external trade shocks than China in three key supply chains: semiconductors, raw materials, and net-zero technologies. The USA are more vulnerable than the EU for raw materials and net-zero technologies. However, they can offset these vulnerabilities with their dominant position in several components of digital infrastructures. For example, the EU share of the global ICT market has halved over the past decade (to 10.8%), while the US share has increased by a third (to 38%) (EC 2025a, 14).

These trends not only allowed the Commission to propose wide-ranging legislative interventions in digital markets. They also lent support to a new industrial policy that broke with the traditional neoliberal approach. Instead of focusing exclusively on market-creation measures, EU policies are now increasingly of a market-direction type (Seidl and Schmitz 2024). Specific technologies and supply chains are targeted to address rising geopolitical tensions and preserve a space of strategic autonomy. The old concept of market failure is replaced by the more capacious concept of ‘systemic failure’, justifying state interventions when geopolitical obstacles hinder the autonomous development of the industry (Di Gregorio and Gherardini 2025).

The twin transition fits well the sovereignty discourse: if both the digital and the energy sector are plagued by significant dependencies, a green industrial policy is the best (apparently the only) answer. Though, the market-direction approach is far from coherent. More traditional market-creation measures, as well as protectionist measures, can be identified. Even when a market-direction approach is adopted, its contents can reflect divergent opinions on the nature of the problem and the kind of correction to be implemented. For example, it can be argued that the goal of decarbonizing the economy without reducing harmful and unnecessary output is unattainable because of severe resource constraints (Hauge and Hickel 2025).

No less relevant are the constraints that the EU constitutional architecture imposes on the balance between supranational and national competences. In the energy sector, the shared competences envisaged by Art. 194 TFEU are one such constraints. Only Member States can decide what their energy mix should be. Market-direction measures can rely on alternative legal bases, for example Art. 114 TFEU on the Internal Market or Art. 173 TFEU on industrial policy (Hancher and de Hauteclocque 2024). Only the former allows to adopt harmonization measures and was employed to support the low-carbon transition. Other Treaty provisions, related to State aid, cohesion policies, economic governance and innovation policies, can be bended for industrial policy purposes. However, there is no competence for a full-fledged, autonomous EU industrial policy (Dermine and Patrin 2026).

The problems the geopolitical turn of the EU has to face do not exclusively depend on how digital sovereignty is defined. Deeper cleavages related to the heterogeneity of Member States’ interests are likely to dominate the debate. Still, regulatory choices are being made both at EU and Member States levels. Definitional clarity is needed to understand their impact and assess them on normative grounds. The next sub-section advances a proposal in this direction.

4.2 Collective and individual dimensions of sovereignty

Digital sovereignty, technological sovereignty, cyber sovereignty and data sovereignty are often used interchangeably. Their meanings might differ, but defining their boundaries is by no means easy. Three reasons explain why: the disciplinary focus, the geographic focus, and the normative focus.

With regard to the disciplinary focus, the academic literature links the concept of digital sovereignty to specific theoretical frameworks and methodologies. For example, economists are interested in narrowing down the concept of technological sovereignty in order to find measurable variables (e.g. Edler 2024). Computer scientists are interested in linking digital sovereignty to the functionalities of specific technologies (e.g., with regard to data spaces, DSSC 2025). Each meaning can fulfil useful purposes in each discipline.

At the same time, integrating different concepts of digital sovereignty avoids making regulatory choices that are grounded on just one or a few disciplinary perspectives. To be sure, achieving convergence on a unitary concept of digital sovereignty is neither possible nor desirable. The most fruitful approach is to try to assess the meanings of digital sovereignty by paying attention to the factors that shape them. Consider, for example, the conceptual grid proposed by Hummel et al. (2021). They observe that discussions about digital sovereignty should clarify who the agents involved are, in which contexts the concept is used, which values matter, what obstacles have to be faced and how they should be managed. For each factor, the integration of multiple disciplinary perspectives is possible.

The geographic focus is relevant because a Euro-centric view of digital sovereignty is useless. What defines EU digital sovereignty is its relationship with the other two Great Powers, that is the USA and China, and with the rest of the world, in particular the Global South (Pohle et al. 2025). Each region or coalition of countries seems to be grappling with its own processes of digital governance. Sovereignty concerns are but one component in such processes. Moreover, they do not orient regulatory choices in the same direction. New concepts are molded, sometimes with an explicit non-Western or post-Western bent. This is the case for post-colonial and commons digital sovereignty (Jiang and Belli 2025). While the extension of the geographic focus introduces further complexity in the debate about digital sovereignty, it is clear that EU regulatory choices need to be discussed from the point of view of their impact on non-EU parties. Critical voices already pointed out that the goal of developing digital infrastructures reflecting European values risks reproducing old colonialist dynamics (Rogat 2025).

Finally, the normative focus is needed to assess the soundness of the regulatory choices. Many authors argued that the goal of digital sovereignty is impossible or misguided if it is understood as complete independence or economic protectionism (Lohmann 2024; Nanni et al. 2024). Conversely, digital sovereignty becomes normatively attractive if it helps redress existing vulnerabilities in the digital sphere (Braun and Hummel 2025).

Drawing on the debates sparked by the disciplinary, geographic and normative foci, I propose to distinguish between collective and individual sovereignty as a first step in the assessment of the impact of sovereignty discourse on regulatory choices.

Similar distinctions were proposed in the literature. Fratini et al. (2024) identify a rights-based model of digital sovereignty, aimed at reinforcing citizens' rights in the digital space, and contrast it with other three models (market-oriented, state-based and centralization) emphasizing the collective dimensions. Adler-Niessen and Eggeling (2024) discuss how discursive claims about digital sovereignty related to collective dimensions, like supporting European tech champions and fostering European security, stand in tension with discursive claims related to individual dimensions, like personal privacy and data ownership. The two dimensions can also be connected to the three foci discussed above. For example, in line with the conceptual grid by Hummel et al. (2021), agents, contexts, values, obstacles and management strategies can be discussed both with regard to collective and individual sovereignty.

More specifically, regulatory interventions related to collective sovereignty are supposed to include one or more of the following aspects:

- a) Restrictions for non-EU companies;

- b) Support for frontier technologies;
- c) Focus on all segments of supply chains;
- d) Contribution to the twin transition.

Conversely, regulatory interventions related to individual sovereignty are supposed to include one or more of the following aspects:

- a) Restrictions for non-EU companies;
- b) Reinforcement or extension of individual rights;
- c) Balancing criteria that leave room for individual rights;
- d) Contribution to the twin transition.

The four aspects highlighted for each dimension represent the most visible targets for policies centering on digital sovereignty.

Admittedly, other targets are possible. The ones discussed in this report should provide a preliminary understanding of where digital sovereignty is heading. At least in theory, all types of regulatory interventions should reduce EU dependencies. Collective sovereignty would be enhanced if the EU economy relied less on foreign suppliers of key technologies. Strengthening individual sovereignty should force non-EU countries and companies to align their regulatory frameworks to the EU one to access the Internal Market.

Moreover, both the collective and the individual dimensions should foster the twin transition. This means that they should contribute to the displacement of environmentally unsustainable technologies and the uptake of digital innovations. However, the collective and individual dimensions could also clash. If they pull in opposite directions, the net effect could be to slow down both transitions. The sovereignty discourse could increase the investment costs of the twin transition by reducing access to cheaper resources and technologies from outside the EU (Arcand and Meadowcroft 2025). Alternatively, security concerns could lead to delay deeper decarbonization, either because the phase out of fossil fuels is postponed, or because the goal of reducing dependencies is pursued by shifting costs to other countries. In both cases, the partnerships needed to coordinate supply chains for clean technologies could be more difficult to develop (Proedrou 2025, 125f.). Even though protectionist policies could in theory spur global competition and prompt more countries to invest in clean technologies, a ‘Green Cold War Scenario’ seems more likely to dash hopes of global decarbonization (Meckling 2025).

More generally, attempts at reducing dependencies by extending the EU regulatory regimes extra-territorially could be less successful for digital infrastructures and clean technologies than was the case in the past for other products. To put it bluntly, rising geopolitical tensions could weaken the ‘Brussels effect’ (Hoch and Mügge 2025; Pagallo 2025; Almada 2025). The following two sections discuss these frictions, and the opportunities for coordinating the collective and individual dimensions, in the areas of cybersecurity and data protection.

5. Digital sovereignty and cybersecurity

This section maps the influence of sovereignty concerns in the cybersecurity legislation. Apparently, the connection between digital sovereignty and cybersecurity is easy to spot: to subtract themselves from foreign influence or control, countries or regions must invest in the protection of government systems, military infrastructure, and critical sectors from cyberattacks or espionage, as well as personal data and national sensitive data from external surveillance or exploitation (Katsikas 2025). If the development of the EU industrial policy is added to the picture, investments in cybersecurity are also supported to strengthen the competitiveness of EU companies in the global market for digital technologies.

The same approach can be extended to the energy sector. The latter is usually at the center of debates about cybersecurity strategies. One reason is its high number of interdependencies with the rest of the economy. Another reason is the ongoing digitalization process of electric grids. As observed in sec. 3.1, new software

and hardware components are being added to existing infrastructures. Sensors, controllers and meters make available new data which help improve grid performance.

Digitalization is also one of the factors enabling the decentralization of energy systems, with a larger number of subjects being involved in producing and trading electricity and energy services. But increasing digital interconnections also increase vulnerabilities. Lack of protection in any device connected to the grid might expose large portions of the electricity system to significant damages. This is the so-called weakest-link problem: an interconnected energy system is just as robust as its weakest node. Therefore, the risk of intentional or unintentional cyber incidents is directly dependent on the degree of integration between energy and information infrastructures.

These observations might suggest that digital sovereignty is extremely valuable: it fosters at the same time innovation and security. However, this nexus can be problematized in several ways (Haddad et al. 2024). Innovation can be argued to represent the solution to security problems or, conversely, the main source of new risks and threats. Furthermore, security issues could prompt innovations or, conversely, prevent innovation because access to knowledge, technologies or networks is forbidden. One of these perspectives could become dominant, for example because of a sudden crisis, but it is more likely that each of the four perspectives contributes to shape some aspects of the cybersecurity regulatory framework. When interdependencies are believed to represent a threat to sovereignty, regulatory goals follow the logic of regulatory mercantilism (Farrand et al. 2024): instead of intervening to foster economic efficiency, regulation aims at gaining control of digital technologies and reducing the influence of companies or foreign countries. The main problem with this approach is that innovation and security do not always march together. If the latter is prioritized, the former might be dampened.

No less relevant are the possible conflicts between the collective and individual dimensions in the field of cybersecurity. A well-known example is the conflict between security, requiring access to all data, and data protection. We shall come back to this conflict in sec. 6.

Other conflicts are possible, for example because confidentiality prevents the identification of public or private entities to be held accountable for cyber harms, or because some citizens or companies are discriminated against on security grounds (van de Poel 2020). With specific regard to critical infrastructures, including energy ones, several value conflicts were identified by Viganò e al. (2020). They relate to the dangerous feedback loops started by increased investments in digitalization. The latter leads to heightened perceptions of insecurity and prompts states to strengthen their cyber defence. However, the same reactions can be expected from potential adversaries, thus contributing to reduce trust at international level. Furthermore, citizens can be harmed by increased surveillance in their home country, increased risk of cyber-attacks by foreign enemies, and higher costs of cyber defences they have to bear individually.

These critical arguments do not sever the tie between digital sovereignty and cybersecurity. Though, they do show that such a connection is much looser than suggested by EU's and Member States' cybersecurity strategies. As observed by Fouad (2025), any information system is marked by inherent uncertainty. Communication channels are always noisy, hence non-linear dynamics can be expected. They prevent any such system from being evaluated as secure or not secure. In place of this binary logic, a process of progressive improvement is the best that can be hoped for. Transposed to the digital sovereignty debate, the inherent uncertainty of information systems suggests that regulatory choices can be interpreted as the best available response to a state of permanent insecurity in a given institutional context. Within the constraints of these non-linear dynamics, the governance of cybersecurity might sometimes succeed in reducing dependencies by fostering innovation. However, it is more likely that governance systems will struggle with the riddle of value conflicts emerging from the interplay between the collective and individual dimensions of sovereignty.

Even when cybersecurity is associated with the economic concept of public good, those value conflicts do not disappear. There is general agreement that, at least with regard to the protection of fundamental economic and social processes from cyber-attacks, the two requirements of non-excludability and non-rivalry can be identified (Taddeo 2019; Brighi and Chiara 2021; Kianpour et al. 2022). At the same time, cybersecurity is not a simple, but a complex public good: it is difficult to define and measure cost, quality, and effectiveness, as

well as to coordinate among the multitude of actors involved (Kianpour and Frantz 2025). This means that the public good concept does not immediately suggest which standards to implement and how to distribute costs among stakeholders. It also means that, faced with a high degree of uncertainty, the addressees of cybersecurity regulation will find it difficult to identify the optimal level of investments. They will choose strategically when and how to comply (Kianpour and Raza 2024).

In this section, we begin to test the relevance of sovereignty concerns with regard to EU horizontal legislation (sec. 5.1). Sector-specific legislation for the energy sector is discussed in sec. 5.2. The roles played by the collective and the individual sovereignty dimensions are discussed in sec. 5.3. The Italian cybersecurity governance is discussed in sec. 5.4.

5.1 Horizontal cybersecurity legislation

EU legislation addresses cybersecurity issues in two domains: infrastructures and products (Table 1). Both domains are relevant to the energy sector. In the domain of infrastructures, three legislative measures were adopted.

Cybersecurity risks are addressed by Dir. 2022/2555 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union (NIS2), physical risks by Dir. 2022/2557 on the resilience of critical entities (CER). The lists of energy sector operators within the scope of the two Directives are aligned and explicit coordination mechanisms are envisaged.

The third measure is Reg. 2025/38 (Cyber Solidarity Act or CSoA). Its main goal is to strengthen EU's capabilities for a coordinated response to cyber threats that could lead to large-scale incidents. Three actions are planned: the deployment of a pan-European infrastructure of Security Operations Centres (European Cyber Shield) to build and enhance common detection and situational awareness capabilities; the creation of a Cyber Emergency Mechanism to support Member States in preparing for, responding to and quickly recovering from significant and large-scale cybersecurity incidents; the establishment of a European Cybersecurity Incident Review Mechanism to review and assess specific significant or large-scale incidents. Sectors of high criticality according to the NIS2 Dir. will be eligible to receive financial support for coordinated preparedness testing at Union level (Art. 12 CSoA).

Table 1 - Horizontal cybersecurity legislation in the EU.

EU legislation - Infrastructures	Italian implementing measures
Dir. 2022/2555 (NIS2)	Legislative Decree no. 138/2024
Dir. 2022/2557 on resilience of critical entities (CER)	Legislative Decree no. 134/2024
Reg. 2025/38 Cyber Solidarity Act (CSoA)	Additional Italian legislation

	Law no. 133/2019 Law no. 90/2024 Law no. 56/2012 Legislative Decree no. 36/2023
EU legislation - Products	Italian implementing measures
Reg. 2019/881 Cybersecurity Act (CSA)	Law no. 109/2021 Legislative Decree no. 123/2022
Reg. 2024/2847 Cyber Resilience Act (CRA)	
Reg. 2024/1689 (AI Act)	Law no. 132/2025
Reg. 2024/1735 Net-Zero Industry Act (NZIA)	

In the products domain, two legislative measures were adopted.

The first one is Reg. 2019/881 (Cybersecurity Act or CSA), which introduced a new European cybersecurity certification framework. It establishes certification schemes which attest compliance of ICT products, services and processes with specified security requirements. Each certification scheme includes a comprehensive set of rules, technical requirements, standards and procedures. It represents an alternative to the adoption of product- and service-specific EU cybersecurity standards, deemed impracticable because of the high variety of security needs and employment modes across sectors. The main goal of the certification scheme is to evaluate if the specified security requirements are met. Though, using certified products, services and processes will be purely voluntary. Mandatory schemes could be introduced in the future following an assessment by the Commission (Art. 56 CSA). For the time being, the main incentive to the adoption of a scheme is to make it easier to prove compliance with the NIS2 Directive. The first such scheme (Reg. 2024/482) referred to ICT products, for example technological components, both hardware and software. A second scheme, related to cloud services, faced significant opposition and is still being discussed (see sec. 5.2).

In 2025, the Commission launched a consultation on the revision of the CSA. Manufacturers of energy technologies complained that digital components of critical energy infrastructures, from solar inverters to EV chargers, smart heat pumps, smart meter gateways, battery management systems and home management systems were exposed to cyberthreats but were not covered by EU-wide certification schemes. More generally, the European solar industry documents that photovoltaic systems are exposed to multiple risks, in particular with regard to remote control by non-trusted parties or in foreign countries (Solar Power Europe 2025).

The second product-related measure is Reg. 2024/2847 (Cyber Resilience Act or CRA). It introduces essential cybersecurity requirements for all products with digital components. Stricter conformity assessment procedures are required for products categorized as important or critical. Smart meter gateways are critical products (Annex IV CRA). But many other products with digital components are widely used in the energy sector with IoT and AI solutions. It is likely that the essential requirements of the CRA will be met in the future with the certificates issued according to the CSA (ENISA 2025a).

Other EU legislative measures include cybersecurity provisions falling within the products domain.

The AI Act (Reg. 2024/1689) explicitly refers to cybersecurity requirements for high-risk AI systems (Art. 15) and for general-purpose AI systems with systemic risks (Art. 55). AI systems employed as safety components of critical infrastructures, as defined in the CER Dir., belong to the high-risk category (Annex III.2 AI Act). Compliance with the essential cybersecurity requirements of the CRA is required for high-risk AI systems but can be satisfied with the conformity assessment of Art. 43 AI Act. A derogation was introduced for important and critical products: they shall be subject to the conformity assessment procedures of the CRA (Art. 12(3) CRA and Recital 78 AI Act). Moreover, high-risk AI systems can fulfil the cybersecurity requirements of the AI Act with a certification scheme adopted according to the CSA (Art. 42(2) AI Act). For general-purpose AI

systems, adherence to a code of practice can be used to prove compliance. The first version of the Code of Practice for general-purpose AI Models, published by the AI Office (2025), includes detailed commitments on cybersecurity.

Market surveillance tasks are entrusted to the national authorities designed according to the AI Act (Art. 52(14) CRA). No coordination provisions were included for general-purpose AI systems with systemic risks. Novelli et al. (2024) suggest that such systems should be included in Annex III of the CRA, so as to qualify as important products. The authors also point out that all AI systems, as well as the services they provide, should be required to address cybersecurity risks. They argue that this outcome could be achieved by applying the cybersecurity and notification requirements of the NIS2 Dir. to AI systems employed by critical entities. Note, however, that products relying on AI systems can be said to fall within the definition of products with digital elements (Art. 3(1) CRA). Therefore, energy companies will be bound to only deploy AI systems that comply with the essential cybersecurity requirements of the CRA (Jørgensen and Ma 2025b, 11). The arguments by Novelli et al. (2024) remain valid to the extent that higher requirements are needed in the energy sector.

Also interesting are the cybersecurity provisions in Reg. 2024/1735 (Net-Zero Industry Act or NZIA). For public procurement procedures related to net-zero technologies, Member States are required to comply with the CRA requirements, including, where appropriate and where available, through a relevant European cybersecurity certification scheme (Art. 25(3)(b) NZIA). Furthermore, Member States are required to adopt pre-qualification criteria related to cybersecurity and data security when designing auctions for renewable energy technologies. These criteria shall apply to at least 30% of the volume auctioned per year per Member State or, alternatively, to at least six Gigawatt per year per Member State (Art. 26(1)(ii) and 26(7) NZIA). Art. 5 of the implementing Reg. 2025/1176 specifies the criteria. Bidders shall adopt cybersecurity risk management measures, reflect them in a cybersecurity plan and ensure those measures are applicable to ICT products or services provided by their suppliers. Where relevant, the measures can include those listed in Art. 21(2) NIS2 for essential and important entities. When the bidder is subject to the jurisdiction of a third country, or there is evidence that malicious cyber activities are carried out by threat actors operating in that third country, it shall ensure that data used for or generated in their business activities related to the auction are stored and processed in the European Economic Area (EEA) and not transferred outside the EEA.

5.2 Cybersecurity in the energy sector

We now turn to sector-specific provisions. They can be grouped in three clusters (Table 2).

The first cluster includes the provisions on the electricity market (Dir. 2019/944 and Reg. 2019/943) and the gas and hydrogen markets (Dir. 2024/1788 and Reg. 2024/1789). The second cluster includes the provisions on security of gas supply (Reg. 2017/1938) and risk-preparedness in the electricity sector (Reg. 2019/941). The third cluster includes the provisions of the network code on cybersecurity of cross-border electricity flows (NCCS: Reg. 2024/1366). Let us consider each cluster.

Table 2 - Cybersecurity legislation for the EU energy sector.

EU legislation	Italian implementing measures
First cluster - Markets Dir. 2019/944 Reg. 2019/943 Dir. 2024/1788 Reg. 2024/1789	Legislative Decree no. 210/2021
Second cluster - Security Reg. 2017/1938 Reg. 2019/941	
Third cluster -NCCS Reg. 2024/1366	Art. 16-quater Law no. 166/24

The provisions in the first cluster address the security of smart metering systems, the responsibilities of transmission system operators, the duty of the ENTSOs and the DSO Entities to promote cybersecurity, as well as the establishment of network codes on matters related to cybersecurity.

In the second cluster we find provisions on both resilience and cybersecurity. Reg. 2017/1938 asks Member States to adopt preventive action plans and emergency plans, lays down procedures for the declaration of a gas supply crisis and lists the responses to be implemented. Reg. 2019/941 follows a similar structure. It asks Member States to adopt risk-preparedness plans covering both national and regional risks. It also lays down rules for managing electricity crisis situations, in cooperation with other Member States and through market and non-market measures. Fair compensation has to be paid to the Member State providing assistance in crisis situations.

Recitals in both Regulations underline the complementarity with critical infrastructure protection and disaster management. However, their most significant change is the transfer of risk prevention and management tasks to regional or EU-wide bodies. More specifically, ENTSO-E and ENTSO-G are charged with the task of developing security of supply indicators and risk assessment methodologies. The Gas Coordination Group and the Electricity Coordination Group, composed of representatives of Member States, ACER, ENTSOs, the industry and relevant consumers, shall coordinate the national security measures and plans. Moreover, in the gas sector regional risk groups shall enable agreement on cross-border measures, in the electricity sector the Regional Coordination Centres (Art. 35-47 Reg. 2019/943) are entitled to perform functions related to both risk assessment and risk prevention.

Cybersecurity risks have to be included in the risk-preparedness plans required by Reg. 2019/941 for the electricity sector (see Recital 7 and Art. 10) and in the risk assessments, preventive action plans and emergency plans required by Reg. 2017/1938 for the gas sector (Art. 8a and 9, as amended by Reg. 2024/1789). The Commission (EC 2019a) issued a recommendation on cybersecurity in the energy sector, aimed at providing guidance to Member States on the implementation of cybersecurity preparedness measures.

Neither the CER Dir. nor the NIS2 Dir. replace the sector-specific obligations for the energy sector. The CER Dir. refers to the risk assessments required by both Reg. 2017/1938 and Reg. 2019/941 and asks Member States to take them into account when identifying critical entities and describing their resilience measures. However, requirements, supervision and enforcement introduced by the CER Dir. should not apply to energy companies when Member States recognize that sector-specific requirements for resilience are at least equivalent to those of the CER Dir. (Art. 1(3)). Also excluded is the specific oversight regime for critical entities of particular European significance which operate in six or more Member States (Art. 17 CER). The CER Dir. should, however, influence the assessment of interdependencies between the energy sector and other sectors. Moreover, the CER Dir. could entail additional obligations related to climate resilience measures for energy infrastructures.

The NIS2 Dir. grants priority to the sector-specific provisions of the energy sector for cybersecurity risk-management measures and notification obligations, to the extent they are equivalent in effect (Art. 4). Commission's guidelines (EC 2023c) clarify how the equivalence between the NIS2 Dir. and sector-specific provisions on cybersecurity should be assessed. Coordination between the sector-specific authorities and the NIS2 authorities is required.

The third cluster includes the provisions related to the NCCS. It aims at establishing a recurrent process of cybersecurity risk assessments in the electricity sector. These assessments are aimed at systematically identifying the entities that perform digitalised processes with a critical or high impact in cross-border electricity flows, their cybersecurity risks, and then the necessary mitigating measures. The code establishes a governance model that uses and is aligned with existing mechanisms established in the NIS2 Dir.. For example, reporting of cyberattacks and vulnerabilities takes place through the established Computer Security Incident Response Teams (CSIRTs), while coordination with the CyCLONe network (Art. 16 NIS2 Dir.) is

required in case of large-scale cybersecurity incidents and crises. Furthermore, the code takes into account the risk preparedness plans and the regional electricity crisis scenarios of Reg. 2019/941.

The implementation of the NCCS will take several years. The energy companies falling within its scope belong to the same categories already listed in the NIS2 Dir.. Note, however, that the scope of the NIS2 Dir. is delineated according to the size of the entities, while in the NCCS reference is made to the thresholds for critical or high impact (DSO Entity and ENTSO-E 2025b). This means that large companies will have to comply with both the NCCS and the NIS2 Dir., while some smaller companies might have to only comply with the NCCS. Rec. 15 NCCS suggests that national authorities could avoid a double burden by requiring compliance with only one of these two legal frameworks.

It can be expected that influences between the horizontal and the energy frameworks will be reciprocal, depending on which one proves more successful in addressing cybersecurity risks. However, it is already clear that, together with the other sector-specific provisions, the NCCS will establish a parallel regulatory framework largely replacing the horizontal cybersecurity framework. The main reason behind the increasing density of the sector-specific regulatory framework can be identified in the need to track the developments in the organization of energy supply chains and markets. The simultaneous transformations brought by the twin transition do not allow to rely on cybersecurity solutions designed for more stable environments. If the relationships along the energy supply chains are radically altered, new vulnerabilities are likely to surface.

5.3 Collective and individual dimensions of cybersecurity

Are sovereignty concerns visible in the horizontal and sector-specific regulatory frameworks for cybersecurity? Yes, but they are unevenly addressed in each legislative measure.

Starting from collective sovereignty, Table 3 shows that horizontal legislation addresses all four aspects identified in sec. 3.2. Restrictions to non-EU companies stem from recourse to European certification schemes or qualified trust services (Art. 24 NIS2 Dir., 46 CSA), the use of European or international standards and technical specifications (Art. 25 NIS2 Dir., 16 CER Dir.), dependency from entities within third countries as one of the factors entering risk assessment (Art. 5(2)(c) and 12(2) CER Dir.), and the link between jurisdictional powers and the territory of a Member State (Art. 26 NIS2 Dir., 14(7) CRA). Conditions for mutual recognition agreements with third countries (e.g. Art. 54(1)(t) CSA, 44 Reg. 2024/482, 34 CRA) are another solution that could address sovereignty concerns. The significance of cybersecurity risks can be assessed with regard to non-technical risk factors, such as the undue influence of a third country on the manufacturer (Rec. 58 and Art 54(2), 54(6) CRA). The procurement procedures for the establishment of the EU Cybersecurity Reserve (Art. 17 CsoA) seem to restrict the participation of non-EU companies.

Table 3. Collective sovereignty in horizontal cybersecurity legislation.

EU legislation	Restrictions to non-EU companies	Frontier tech	Supply chains	Twin transitions
CSA	Art. 8, 12(d), 46, 54(1)(t), 67(3) Art. 44 Reg. 2024/482	Art. 4(5-6), 9(a), 11	Rec. 4	-
NIS2 Dir.	Art. 24, 25, 26	Art. 7(2)(e)	Art. 21(2)(d), 22	-
Critical entities Dir.	Art. 5(2)(c), 12(2), 16	Art. 17(3)(i)	Art. 13(1)(d)	Art. 7(1)(c)
CRA	Art. 5(2), 14(7), 34, 54(2), 56(2)	Art. 31(5), 32(6), 33, 39(12), 47(2)	Art. 8(2)(b), 13(5), 25, Annex I.II(6)	-
CsoA	Art. 17	Art. 1(2), 3(1)(c)		-
AIA	Art. 15, 55	Art. 58(2)(i)	Rec. 114	-
NZIA	Art. 25(3)(b), 26(1)(a)(ii)	-	-	-

	Art. 5, 16(4) Reg. 2025/1176			
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Frontier technologies are supported by requiring Member States to develop and integrate advanced solutions for cybersecurity risk-management (Art. 7(2)(d) NIS2 Dir.), tasking ENISA to increase cybersecurity capabilities, strengthening trust in the digital internal market and its competitiveness (Art. 4(5-6) CSA), and advising on research and innovation (Art. 11 CSA), as well as by establishing regulatory sandboxes (Art. 33 CRA, 58(2)(i) AIA).

The European Cyber Alert System is supposed to contribute to innovation through the use of state-of-the-art tools and advanced technologies (Art. 3(2)(c) CSoA). Lighter procedures are required for microenterprises and small and medium enterprises (e.g. Art. 31(5) CRA on the administrative burden of technical documentation and Art. 32(6) CRA on conformity assessment procedures). Explicit reference is made to the concept of supply chain security and to coordinated risk assessment of critical ICT products supply chains (Art. 24 and 25 NIS2 Dir.). A supply chain security policy is required for essential and important entities by implementing Reg. 2024/2690 (ENISA 2025b). Manufacturers shall exercise due diligence when integrating components sourced from third parties (Art. 13(5) CRA).

Individual sovereignty, too, is well represented in horizontal cybersecurity legislation (Table 4). Compliance with data protection provisions is always required. Examples of balancing assessments can be found in the requirement to protect personal data when sharing information between essential and important entities (Art. 20(2) NIS2 Dir.) or critical entities (Art. 10(3) CER Dir.), as well as in the consultation processes involving data protection authorities (Art. 9(5) CER Dir., 7(2) CSA, 52(7) CRA). Users of products with digital components are granted several rights toward manufacturers. The vulnerabilities shall be handed in effectively during the support period, usually lasting five years. Security updates shall remain available for at least ten years or for the remainder of the support period (Art. 13(8)-(9) CRA). Detailed information and instructions have to be provided to the users (Art. 13(18) and Annex II CRA). Manufacturers also have the duty to inform impacted users or all users of actively exploited vulnerabilities or severe incidents having an impact on the security of the product (Art. 14(8) CRA). Disclosure of security issues can also be decided by the national CSIRT (Art. 17(2) CRA). Admittedly, private enforcement mechanisms for users are not well developed. Dir. 2024/2853 on liability for defective products, which refers to safety-relevant cybersecurity requirements (Art. 7(2)(f)), could provide some relief (Chiara 2025). Equally relevant could be the security requirements and the security updates for the conformity of digital contents and digital services supplied to consumers (Art. 8 Dir. 2019/770).

Table 4. Individual sovereignty in horizontal cybersecurity legislation.

EU legislation	Restrictions to non-EU companies	Individual rights	Balancing	Twin transitions
CSA	-	Art. 4(7), 5(5)(c), 10	Art. 7(2)	-
NIS2 Dir.	-	Art. 2(12), 25	Art. 2(14), 17, 29(2)	-
Critical entities Dir.	-	Art. 1(9),	Art. 9(5), 10(3), 14(2)	-
CRA	-	Art. 7(2)(b), 13(8),(9-10),(18-19), 14(8), 17(2), 52(11), 59, 60, 65 Annex I.I(e),(g),(i),(l-m) Annex I.II(4), Annex II	52(7)	-
CsoA	-	Rec. 56	Rec. 26	-
AIA	-	-	Art. 78(2)	-
NZIA	-	Art. 5(b) Reg. 2025/1176	-	-

What about sovereignty concerns in EU energy legislation? A few measures have already been adopted with the markets and security legislation. They aimed at prompting investments in cybersecurity by energy companies and Member States, both to support innovation and to prevent non-EU companies from increasing risks in the Internal Energy Market. At individual level, cybersecurity protections are mentioned with regard to the risks stemming from the rolling out of smart meters and the control of the consumers' data they generate.

Table 5. *Collective sovereignty in the energy sector.*

EU legislation	Restrictions to non-EU companies	Frontier tech	Supply chains	Twin transitions
Markets	-	Art. 40(1)(m) Dir. 2019/944 Art. 30(1)(n), 55(1)(e) Reg. 2019/943 Art. 59(1)(k) Reg. 2024/1789	-	-
Security	-	Art. 10 Reg. 2019/941 Art. 8a, 9 Reg. 2017/1938	-	-
NCCS	Art. 2(3), 14, 15, 36	Art. 13(3)(c)	Art. 18(2)(ii-v), 23(2)(g), 26(4)(a)(ii), 33	-

The bulk of the provisions related to cybersecurity is now included in the NCCS. With regard to restrictions to non-EU companies, the main obligations of the code are extended to all high-impact or critical-impact entities offering services within the EU (Art. 15 NCCS), as well as to neighboring countries (Art. 14 NCCS). When available, European cybersecurity certification schemes should apply, thus forcing non-EU companies to align with EU standards.

Very detailed provisions on cybersecurity controls in the supply chains are included in Art. 33 NCCS. References to supply chains can also be found in the risk assessment methodologies (Art. 18(2)(ii-v) NCCS; also see the list of cyber threats in DSO Entity and ENTSO-E 2024a), in the TSOs' comprehensive cross-border cybersecurity risk assessment report (Art. 23(2)(g) NCCS), and in the cybersecurity risk management to be performed by each high-impact and critical-impact entity (Art. 26(4)(a)(ii) NCCS). The concept of critical ICT service providers is introduced (Art. 3(9) NCCS). The latter bear the cybersecurity obligations laid down by the code. In the provisional list of high-impact and critical-impact processes drawn out by the DSO Entity and the ENTSO-E (2024b, 6), critical ICT service providers include suppliers of SCADA systems, parties with remote access to high- or critical-impact assets, hosting providers or cloud providers, software-as-service providers. This means that a large portion of the ICT supply chain has to comply with the sector-specific obligations of the NCCS when supplying services to high-impact and critical-impact entities. Whether energy companies are going to invest in frontier technologies will at least partly depend on cost recovery principles for network tariffs (Art. 11 NCCS). The non-binding benchmarking guide (Art. 13 NCCS; ACER 2025c) refers to cybersecurity technological investments, but it seems to prioritize efficiency in spending over innovation.

With regard to the individual dimension, Art. 2(6) NCCS states that processing of personal data can take place for the purposes of the code and according to the legal bases of Art. 6 Reg. 2016/679 (GDPR). This means that consent of the data subject is usually not required (see also Rec. 33 NCCS). The protection of personal data is specifically addressed by the ACER's guidelines on confidentiality of information (ACER 2025b).

Table 6. Individual sovereignty in the energy sector.

EU legislation	Restriction to non-EU companies	Individual rights	Balancing	Twin transitions
Markets	-	-	Art. 20(b) Dir. 2019/944 Art. 19(b) Dir. 2024/1788	-
Security	-	Art. 11(1)(h) Reg. 2019/941	-	-
NCCS	-	-	Art. 2(6)	-

Three general observations can be made. First, restrictions on non-EU companies are supposed to be offset with larger investments in innovative cybersecurity technologies by Member States and EU companies. The regulatory mercantilist approach, linking economic competitiveness and security, is visible here (Farrand et al. 2024). This is also a clear example of regulation-induced innovation: stricter obligations should lead to an increase of the innovation rate. However, there are well-known limits to such a strategy, the most important one being that sustained innovation only takes place within national or regional ecosystems comprised of several types of public and private actors, knowledge formation and diffusion tools, market formation strategies, as well as supportive institutions (March and Schieferdecker 2023). The current regulatory framework contributes only indirectly to building such ecosystems (with regard to the NIS2 Dir. see Kianpour et al. 2025).

Controls on supply chains are needed to reduce vulnerabilities (ENISA 2023; WEF 2025). But compliance hinges on some degree of convergence between EU and non-EU regulatory frameworks. Without convergence, suppliers located in more lenient jurisdictions could invest less, hoping that companies located in stricter jurisdictions will provide a good enough level of cybersecurity for the whole chain. These interdependencies could lead to under- or overinvestments in cybersecurity, depending on the expected impact of cyber-attacks (Fedele and Roner 2022).

Moreover, the unilateral imposition of cyber defences by the chain leader to the suppliers could raise concerns both from the point of view of competition law and of rules against the abuse of economic dependence (Iwasaki 2024). EU legislation tries to avoid burdening small companies with too high costs of cyber defences, but many suppliers in relevant chains could be small companies. This means that chain leaders should be given incentives to bear all investment costs. Of course, the digital dependency of EU companies from non-EU suppliers could often mean that they do not enjoy the bargaining power allowing them to include the contractual obligations on cybersecurity required by the supply chain security policy (Annex to Reg. 2024/2690). Hence, regulatory choices are coherent with the sovereignty narrative, but their effectiveness in promoting both innovation and security is debatable.

Second, almost no connection is made between the regulatory framework for cybersecurity and the low-carbon transition. Only Art. 7(1)(c) CER Dir. hints at the risk that incidents could have an impact on the environment. There is, however, no mention of other two problems: on one hand, the inadequacy of cybersecurity requirements to protect the environment; on the other hand, the possibility that cyber defences could lead to an increase of greenhouse gases emissions or other environmental impacts.

Third, even though individual sovereignty is somewhat strengthened, both financial and informational support provided to users is quite limited. It is doubtful that all users will be put into the position to make sound choices about the cybersecurity investments needed. As already pointed out, private enforcement mechanisms for violations of cybersecurity requirements were not strengthened. With specific regard to the energy sector, the crucial aspect is that digitalization is meant to make it possible to decentralize production and enable consumers' active participation in electricity markets. Though, the new role of prosumers or active consumers requires an additional investment in cybersecurity.

The decentralization of energy systems increases the complexity of communications and interactions. Digital technologies are needed to manage both distribution networks and distributed energy resources. But new types of cyber threats have to be managed (Chen et al. 2025). Smart meters could be vulnerable if they use weak encryption algorithms, weak authentication mechanisms or insecure communication protocols (Nambundo et al. 2025). Peer-to-peer energy sharing between prosumers can be protected with distributed ledger technologies, but the latter do not prevent some types of cyber-attacks, for example false data injection, denial of service, or theft of energy consumption data (Sousa-Dias et al. 2023). The authentication required to recharge electric vehicles can be taken over by adversaries (Zografopoulos et al. 2023). Energy communities could be vulnerable to cyber-attacks targeting the communication protocols used by prosumers, the smart gateway connecting the prosumers to the energy community platform, and the platform itself. The attacks could succeed in injecting or withdrawing electricity from the grid in order to create unbalances and service interruptions (Gaggero et al. 2023; Ricciuti et al. 2024; Mokarim et al. 2024).

The EU regulatory framework does not provide satisfactory answers to the cybersecurity risks of decentralized energy systems. As pointed out by Petruolo et al. (2025), if prosumers collectively contribute a significant portion of the energy supply, their role becomes more critical, potentially elevating their status to essential entities. Prosumers themselves can be the vectors of cyber-attacks (Coppolino et al. 2025).

Furthermore, control of prosumer devices can be located in non-EU jurisdictions without any cybersecurity oversight. Though, prosumers and energy communities could be outside the scope of the NCCS if they do not reach the impact thresholds. They could also be outside the scope of the NIS2 Dir. because they are below the ceilings for medium-sized enterprises (Art. 2(1) NIS2 Dir.). For the time being, prosumers do not have obligations related to cybersecurity requirements but depend for their own cybersecurity on the investments made by network operators, energy companies and ICT companies. This means that prosumers pay for cyber protection through network tariffs and the price of energy and digital services but have little control on investments in cybersecurity. If cybersecurity qualifies as a public good, transparent criteria to fund it should be put in place. Consumers and prosumers should not be required to shoulder the entire cost of protection measures.

To summarize: in the field of cybersecurity, the collective dimension of digital sovereignty is already well developed. However, there are several reasons to doubt that measures aimed at imposing restrictions on non-EU companies and to control ICT supply chains will be effective in both reducing cyber risks and fostering innovation. Almost completely lacking is an attempt to develop synergies between the twin transition. Conversely, the individual dimension of cybersecurity is far from becoming one of the main goals, both in horizontal legislation and in the energy sector.

5.4 Cybersecurity in the Italian legislation

Do sovereignty concerns only surface at EU level? Or are Member States equally supportive of the new interventionist stance? Do they go beyond what is required by EU law? Political science studies pointed out that France and Germany already brought sovereignty issues to the fore in the 2010s, with the full endorsement by the Commission shortly thereafter (sec. 4.1). This could be an example of the transfer of national security concerns to the EU level. Note, however, that sensitive competence issues are at play here. As mentioned in sec. 4.2, the EU relied on its competences on the Internal Market and industrial policy to significantly expand the reach of the supranational regulatory framework for digital technologies. Though, national security falls within the exclusive competence of Member States (Art. 4(2) TEU). At least in theory, national provisions on cybersecurity could diverge from EU provisions if justified on national security grounds. However, the broader EU framework put in place since the end of the 2010s blurred the boundaries between the market logic and the national security logic (Matassa 2025). The question today is whether and how Member States decide to adopt additional measures addressing the collective and individual dimensions of sovereignty. It is also important to understand how Member States balance innovation and cybersecurity. It cannot be excluded they introduce measures that make intra-EU cooperation more difficult.

Italy represents a good testbed for the relevance of sovereignty concerns at Member State level. Two features can be highlighted. First, Italy has a high level of digital dependency (see sec. 4.1). Second, it is among the countries most affected by cyber-attacks. In 2024, cyber incidents in Italy represented about 10% of the global sample. Smaller figures were observed in other industrialized countries like France, Germany and the UK (Clusit 2025, 32; Bussetti and Scanni 2025). Not surprisingly, these two features prompted several legislative interventions aimed not only at implementing EU measures, but also at designing effective governance mechanisms at national level. In the ITU's Global Cybersecurity Index 2024, monitoring countries' level of cybersecurity commitments, Italy scores among the role-modelling countries showing coordinated and government-driven actions that encompass generally accepted cybersecurity measures.

To be sure, this data only provides a partial picture about the relevance of cyber threats and the effectiveness of the regulatory frameworks. Having in place mandatory measures says little about real compliance. For example, Italian companies falling within the remit of the NIS2 Dir. appear to spend more on security than French and German companies, but less on more advanced solutions like post-quantum cryptography (ENISA 2024, 28, 30). Small companies are more exposed to cyber-attacks (Clusit 2025, 203-211), but at the same time invest less in cybersecurity (I-COM 2025, 104f.).

In this section, we first provide an overview of governance mechanisms, then discuss the provisions that appear to be most directly related to sovereignty concerns.

Two stages in the development of the Italian regulatory framework for cybersecurity can be identified (Ursi 2023; Martino 2024; Baldoni 2025). In the 2010s, cybersecurity was exclusively entrusted to the executive power and managed within the domain of intelligence services. In the 2020s, a national cybersecurity agency (ACN) was established (Law no. 109/21) and became the central institution for cybersecurity governance. The executive power still retained strong control over the work of the ACN and the overall national strategies. However, most aspects related to the evolution of the national infrastructures, and the monitoring of cyber risks were transferred to the ACN. The latter also became the competent authority for the implementation of EU legislation. For example, art. 16-quarter law no. 166/24 designated the ACN as the competent authority for the implementation of the NCCS.

Changes in the cybersecurity policies were far from linear. To a significant extent, they were influenced by strategic choices made by the EU and NATO. Though, some regulatory choices were shaped by national factors. In the 2010s, as soon as the shortcomings of the EU cybersecurity legislation became clear, new legislative measures introduced the so called 'perimeter for national cybersecurity' (Law no. 133/2019). It significantly broadened the range of private and public subjects to be considered relevant for the protection of national security. They are the entities performing a material function (*funzione essenziale*) of the state or providing a material service (*servizio essenziale*) that supports civil, social and economic activities of crucial relevance for the state.

In specifying the two concepts, the Decree of the Prime Minister 30 July 2020 included in the material function the governmental activities and the activities of other constitutional bodies, while it referred to the protection of fundamental rights, infrastructures, research activities and economic activities in the field of advanced technologies for the material service. Entities in the energy sector are obviously included in the perimeter, although their identity is not disclosed for security reasons. Moreover, Law no. 133/2019 laid down the main obligations related to the communication of cyber incidents, the security measures to be implemented and the procurement of ICT services, assets and systems. Most provisions related to the perimeter overlap with the obligations later introduced at EU level with the NIS2 Dir. Indeed, in implementing such Directive, Legislative Decree no. 138/24 explicitly states (Art. 33 and 43(2)) that for the entities already included in the perimeter only compliance with the national provisions is required. At the same time, entities included in the perimeter who do not qualify as essential or important entities are included in the scope of application of the NIS2 Dir. (Art. 8-bis Law 133/19).

Further provisions for the national system of cybersecurity governance were introduced with Law no. 90/24, enacted shortly before the implementation of the NIS2 Dir.. The definition of cybersecurity in Art. 1(a) Law no. 109/21 refers to the national interest in the cyber space, perhaps the closest Italian legislation comes to the

concept of digital sovereignty. It seems that Italy wants to affirm an autonomous national policy space for cybersecurity, independent from EU initiatives. The development of the national governance system was also supported with the EU funds allocated to the Italian Recovery and Resilience Plan (ACN 2024b, 77-84). But do the national regulatory choices reflect sovereignty concerns?

Starting with the collective dimension, Art. 27 Legislative Decree no. 138/24 entrusted ACN to introduce mandatory certification schemes for essential and important subjects. This power goes beyond Art. 24(2) NIS2 Dir., allowing the Commission to adopt delegated acts on mandatory schemes. Art. 32 Legislative Decree no. 138/24 allows ACN to impose specific obligations on important and essential entities that provide services, including digital ones, to the public administration. This provision reflects the risks stemming from the high level of digital dependency of the country. Much the same reason can be identified in the extension of the scope of cybersecurity obligations to a larger number of public and private entities (Annexes III and IV Legislative Decree no. 138/24).

Other two areas are relevant from the point of view of restrictions to non-EU companies.

First, broad cybersecurity requirements are introduced in public procurement procedures. The general legal regime applying to all public administrations is laid down by Art. 108(4) Legislative Decree no. 36/23 (Code of Public Contracts or CPC). Elements of cybersecurity have to be taken into account in all cases. When 'strategic national interests' are involved, cybersecurity has to be prioritized and the weight of the economic factors in the adjudication process cannot exceed 10 percent (30 percent in case of high labour intensity). Beyond these general requirements, additional ones shall be complied with in some cases. Art. 1(6)(a) Law no. 133/19 requires the entities included in the perimeter to notify the National Center for Evaluation and Certification the intention to buy ITC assets, systems and services. The Center can order to test hardware and software, forbid the purchase or impose conditions. These provisions were implemented with the Presidential Decree no. 54/21 (evaluation procedures to be employed by the Center) and Decree of the Prime Minister of 15 June 2021 (categories of ICT assets, systems and services). Art. 14 Law no. 90/24 adds that, when strategic national interests are involved, essential cybersecurity requirements have to be adopted in procurement procedures by public entities and private entities included in the perimeter for specific digital assets and services. Reward mechanisms are introduced for offers that ensure the deployment of cybersecurity technologies from Italy, the EU, NATO countries, or other countries with whom the EU or NATO have cooperation agreements in the field of cybersecurity. An explicit reference is made to the goal of technological and strategic autonomy for cybersecurity. An implementing act (Decree of the Prime Minister 30 April 2025) provided the list of essential requirements, the list of specific digital assets and services, and the list of countries with cooperation agreements. Further guidelines on the cybersecurity requirements to be adopted in procurement processes are referred to in the three-year plan for the digitalization of public administrations (AGID 2024).

Doubts are raised about the coordination of the general regime with the more specific regimes for some categories of technologies. No definition of strategic national interests is provided by the legislator (Cocchi 2024; Rossa 2024; Nannipieri 2024, Sferrazzo 2025).

Second, the Italian government can use its special (golden) powers to veto, or impose restrictive conditions on, corporate transactions when they can engender cybersecurity risks (Law no. 56/12). This legal regime largely mirrors similar regimes adopted by the majority of Member States. It also complements the EU measures, in particular Reg. 2019/452 establishing a framework for the screening of direct foreign investments. Two technological domains are directly related to cybersecurity. First, Art. 1-bis Law no. 56/12 delegates the government to identify services, assets, relationships, activities and technologies relevant to cybersecurity for the purpose of exercising the screening powers. So far, this article has not been implemented. Second, investments related to critical technologies in the field of cybersecurity can be screened according to Art. 2(1-ter) Law no. 56/12, which in turn refers to the list of critical technologies in Art. 4(1)(b) Reg. 2019/452. Screening is possible even for operations within the same corporate group. Critical technologies are further specified in Art. 9 of the implementing Decree of the Prime Minister no. 179/20. The annual reports of the Italian government on the use of the special powers show that investments related to cybersecurity are notified,

the use of veto powers is rare, but restrictions are often imposed to foreign investors (see the interventions reported by ACN 2024b, 72f.). In the ongoing revision of Reg. 2019/452, aimed at harmonizing national screening mechanisms, control on investments in cybersecurity is envisaged (EC 2024b, Annex II), with an obligation to notify the investment when the foreign investor meets some risk-related conditions. Neither for Italy nor for the EU there is evidence that screening mechanisms are used for protectionist purposes. However, the broad discretion those mechanisms grant to national governments suggests that both geopolitical and competitive considerations might play a non-secondary role. Moreover, the Italian special powers have been applied to EU companies, thus raising doubts about the impact of restrictions on the Single Market.

Technological innovation is mainly supported through the activities pursued by ACN. Art. 7(1)(r, v, v-bis) Legislative Decree no. 82/21 refers to support for research and educational activities. Art. 7(1)(m-bis) Legislative Decree no. 82/21 requires supporting the national industrial and technological autonomy through the development of proprietary algorithms in the field of cryptographic systems. Art. 7(1)(aa) Legislative Decree no. 82/21 designates ACN as the National Coordination Centre for the participation to the European Cybersecurity Industrial, Technology and Research Competence Centre established with Reg. 2021/887.

Finally, synergies between cybersecurity and decarbonization can be found in the requirements on energy savings and energy efficiency introduced in the regulation on cloud services for Italian public administrations (ACN 2024a)

With regard to the individual dimension, beyond general references to the horizontal regime of the GDPR, it is possible to mention the provisions on the cooperation between the ACN and the Italian data protection authority (Art. 7(5) Law no. 109/21, 14 Legislative Decree no. 138/24), as well as the special regime on personal data to be treated for reasons of national security (Art. 13 Law no. 109/21, Art. 58 Legislative Decree no. 196/2003).

In the national legislation for the energy sector, it is possible to refer to Art. 9(1)(b) Legislative Decree no. 210/21 on the adoption of best available technologies for the security of smart meters. The national energy authority (ARERA) is also required to take costs into account, in line with the proportionality principle. The security policy for processing energy data in the centralized data hub (Integrated Information System or SII) managed by the Single Buyer (a public company) is laid down by Art. 5, Annex A, ARERA dec. 2010/201 and further detailed by the regulation on the functioning of the SII (Single Buyer 2020).

Further references to cybersecurity crises and the procedures to be activated by energy operators can be found in the risk preparedness plan adopted by the Ministry for the environment and energy security with decree of 21 April 2023. For the gas sector, the preventive action plan and the emergency plan adopted in 2019 have to be updated to include the measures related to cybersecurity, as required by the 2024 amendments to Reg. 2017/1938.

Overall, the Italian cybersecurity framework goes beyond the EU provisions under several respects: the scope of the sectors with cybersecurity obligations, the requirements in public procurement procedures, as well as the conditions that can be imposed by the government through the special powers. Notably, this extensive body of rules lacks clarity on the kind of sovereignty to be pursued. References to national strategic interests are frequently made, but their boundaries are not specified. The national cybersecurity strategy (ACN 2022) connects digital sovereignty to technological innovation (Matassa 2022). This approach matches the EU narrative but has to reckon with the complexity of the interactions between the public and the private sectors. Much of the Italian legislation is devoted to the introduction of binding requirements. Less developed are models for public-private partnerships that can avoid unbalanced relationships (Monteleone and Rossi 2024; Pietrangelo 2024; Previti 2025; Terracciano 2025). To pick up one example, in June 2025 the Italian TSO announced an agreement with Microsoft for AI, cloud services and security. For the time being, neither the EU nor the Italian cybersecurity frameworks have led to options that could reduce the dependency of the Italian energy sector from non-EU suppliers.

The ACN is supposed to become the orchestrator of innovation processes. In the Italian law on artificial intelligence no. 132/2025, cybersecurity for the life cycle of AI systems and general purpose systems is

included among the general principles (Art. 3(6)). The ACN is charged with tasks related to the development of AI systems (Art. 18), is designated as the competent authority for the vigilance on AI systems (Art. 20(1)(b), which implements Art. 70 AI Act), and is a member of the national committee coordinating the authorities operating in the field of digital innovation and AI (Art. 19(6)). Explicit reference is made to a preference, in public procurement procedures, for AI systems processing strategic data in data centers located on the national territory (Art. 5(d)). Compliance with the principles of competition, non-discrimination and proportionality is required, but a broad understanding of national interests could in the future justify restrictions toward both EU and non-EU companies. Traces of regulatory mercantilism are visible here. As suggested above, it was promoted by the EU itself. If promoted by a significant number of Member States, it could increase barriers in the Internal Market.

6. Digital sovereignty and data protection

Control over data is said to represent, together with control of clean technologies and networks, one of the sources of geoeconomic power in the low-carbon transition. As already observed in sec. 4.1, the digitalization of energy systems is prompted by the need to exploit data flows to coordinate the different components. It can be added that whoever has access to energy-related data and whose data are considered trustworthy is going to directly affect competition in energy markets at global and regional levels (Quitow and Zabanova 2025).

The biggest problem is that data sovereignty concerns are moving regulatory frameworks towards an increasing number and types of restrictions to free cross-border data flows. The three largest markets (the USA, the EU and China) led the way (Chander 2025). But several other countries adopted restrictive data policies. Trade agreements only partly address these restrictions and only for a minority of countries (Burri et al. 2024). Data flows can be regulated for several reasons, from protecting privacy to controlling cyber risks to preserving economic competitiveness. To an increasing extent, the identity of each legal system is linked to the way it decides to define its priorities in the digital sphere (Smorto 2023). Whether any of these reasons justifies restrictions is debatable. For example, Swire et al. (2024) show that restrictions on cross-border transfers of personal data significantly weaken the effectiveness of cyber defenses. Even assuming that some restrictions are justified, the price tag is high: according to some simulations, data flows restrictions along geopolitical blocks could reduce the global GDP by 1%. A larger negative impact could follow from data flows restrictions in all regions (OECD and WTO 2025). No less controversial is the compatibility of those restrictions with international trade law (Mishra 2024).

The two questions addressed in this section are whether sovereignty concerns surface in the regulatory framework for the management of energy data and how these concerns impact users' rights and more general notions of privacy and data protection in the EU.

To clarify the connection between this section and the previous one, a preliminary distinction has to be made between security and data protection. Data breaches are a well-known example of cyber incidents. Synergies between the two domains can be easily identified: a secure digital environment is an essential prerequisite for the exercise of the rights of data subjects. The security obligations for controllers and processors of personal data in Artt. 32-34 GDPR can be read in this light. The opposite is also true: if the data minimization and integrity and confidentiality principles and legal limits to data processing are complied with, harm from cyber-attacks can be reduced. However, data protection cannot be conflated with security. The former is connected to broader aspects of the individual personality¹ and cannot be said to be protected if only confidentiality of data is ensured. The distinction in the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights between the right to privacy (Art. 7) and the right to data protection (Art. 8) confirms that a broad range of individual interests is involved. At the very least, each data subject should be able to autonomously choose how to manage her personal data. Those

¹ This is applicable to the European legal framework that has been influenced by the debate on privacy as part of the civil law category of "personality rights" ("diritti della personalità" in Italian, "droits de la personnalité" in French, "derechos de la personalidad" in Spanish, etc.). This category groups the individual rights that are granted to a natural person for protecting intimate spheres, private life and personality in a physical and psychological dimension. Other examples of these rights are the right over the name, right on image or right to publicity (Alpa, Resta, 2019).

choices should also be possible for some categories of non-personal data. Needless to say, cross-cultural differences do have an impact on how the autonomy of data subjects is perceived and, consequently, on the likelihood of bridging those differences through international cooperation (Thir and Wawra 2025)

Are the collective and individual dimensions of sovereignty still relevant here? Yes. On the collective side, the restrictions to cross-border data flows mentioned above testify that the EU tries to avoid the economic value of data is captured by foreign parties. On the individual side, the European Strategy for Data explicitly aims at providing data subjects with better decision-making tools (“place the interests of the individual first”: EC 2020a, 1). But keeping together the two dimensions is by no means easy. As already pointed out in sec. 4.2, the notion of data sovereignty does not have a widely agreed meaning. It is likely that promoting the sovereignty of some groups or entities interferes with the sovereignty claims of other groups (Hummel et al. 2021, 14).

As regards general aspects of the data protection framework and digital sovereignty, further considerations are pointed out in the other deliverable for the EMDAS Project “Digital and data sovereignty: the applicable legal frameworks and the case study of the IoT”.

In the energy sector, data protection issues bring to the fore the tensions about the meanings and impacts of digitalization. For example, the most recent smart meters can collect data at 1 second resolution. This means that more sophisticated network and demand side management strategies become possible. At the same time, the risks related to misuse of data increase exponentially. Unless satisfactory answers to the issues related to data protection and the distribution of costs and benefits among different categories of stakeholders are provided, no or little agreement can be expected about the future of smart energy systems (Hargreaves et al. 2022).

It was pointed out that traditional notions of sovereignty tied to territorial control are incompatible with data flowing across national boundaries (Catanzariti 2024, 3). Yet, some concept of sovereignty is needed to assess the increasing number of regulatory measures aimed at controlling data flows. In what follows, we shall argue that two distinct trajectories of data sovereignty can be identified in the energy sector. The first trajectory, discussed in sec. 6.1, displays attention for individual data sovereignty in liberalized energy markets. The second trajectory (sec. 6.2) is strongly connected to the collective dimension of data governance and obscures somewhat the individual dimension. In each section, we shall discuss the interplay of the horizontal and sector-specific legislation on data protection.

6.1 The first trajectory: data protection for energy markets

When investments in smart grids started in the 2000s, the debate focused exclusively on the data protection of the individual user. The main issue was how to ensure control over data generated by smart meters. Later on, the digitalization process took on a broader meaning and required to put in place the infrastructures for the decentralized management of generation resources and networks. At that point, the debate shifted to the organization of energy data markets. In this second period, the protection of individual users’ data is intermingled with, and balanced against, the enhancement of the data flows required by the deployment of digital technologies.

During the early stage of smart meters roll-out, the EU adopted the existing data protection legislation as its main reference point. Although Dir. 2009/73 (the third electricity Directive) did not refer to data protection in the provisions mandating a cost-benefit analysis for smart meters, the national data protection regulators, the European Data Protection Supervisor (EDPS) and consumer representatives quickly pointed out that the implementation of smart grids required careful consideration of personal data processing (Article 29 WP 2011; EDPS 2012; ANEC and BEUC 2010). The Commission endorsed this view (EC 2012, 2014). The Smart Grid Task Force (SGTF) was required to specify how the EU data protection legislation (at that time, mainly Dir. 1995/46 on processing of personal data and Dir. 2002/58 on privacy in electronic communications) would

apply in the energy sector. A template for voluntary Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs) (SGTF 2018) and best available techniques for the security and privacy of smart meters (SGTF 2016) were drafted. Much the same approach was visible in the smart grid standardization mandates: data protection legislation acted as one of the parameters to be implemented in the communication interfaces linking energy consumers and data controllers (EC 2009, 2011). To some extent, the energy sector proved a testbed for solutions (from privacy by design to DPIAs) later to be adopted with the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR)².

Did such a legal framework ensure the smooth transition to smart meters? In many Member States, the answer was negative. Opposition to their installation was widespread. Fears of privacy breaches were among the most common concerns. This is a little bit surprising, given the broad scope of EU data protection legislation. This is particularly true if one reflects on the broad notion of “personal data”, which also includes information indirectly related to a natural person (art. 4 GDPR). Several studies documented a deeper issue: smart meters, and digitalization more generally, change the way the interaction between consumers and energy services providers is organized. Such change involves energy consumption habits, perceptions of control on personal data and security from unwanted intrusions in the private sphere, as well as the distribution of costs and benefits. For many years, national smart meters programs struggled to manage all these aspects while complying with the complex rules of the data protection framework.

The diffusion of Internet of Things (IoT) and AI in energy markets greatly increased the range of possible services. At the same time, it also required to regulate additional data flows. While in the earlier period the conflict between data protection and data access and sharing (internally and externally) could be addressed from the perspective of the individual consumer, at a later stage the balance of competing interests has to be sought in the organization of energy markets. Also, the governance of energy data is influenced by developments in the horizontal regulatory frameworks that address the broader transformations of the digital economy. Those frameworks are discussed in sec. 6.2. In the balance of this section, we describe the data protection issues arising from the deployment of digital technologies in the energy sector.

Consider IoT approaches first. When they are implemented in the energy sector, the main goal is the same as in other sectors: to collect the largest possible amount of data and use it to address communication and cooperation needs. Sensors embedded in appliances and infrastructures collect energy data and process them in clouds or in decentralized computation resources. From a data protection perspective, at least two categories of concerns can be identified.

First, data can be used to manipulate users’ behaviour. Studies on smart home devices show that up to 90 different dark patterns, designed to trick users into unwanted or unintentional behaviour, can be detected (Kowalczyk et al. 2023). The same manipulation risk arises when data are collected with smart meters: they can reveal consumption habits, availability of electric appliances, and mobility patterns. If aggregated with data from other smart appliances, smart meters data can contribute to users’ profiling and lead to even more sophisticated marketing strategies. Profiling and marketing purposes should be clearly defined in the privacy policy and accepted by the user with an expression of consent (Artt. 12-14 GDPR). However, the practices are frequently complex to be described and indirectly carried out because data is processed and derived by mixed datasets.

Second, the distinction between personal and non-personal data is largely blurred. Even when only data related to machine tasks is collected, it can be used to infer personal data or profile users. Hence, the applications of IoT approaches should fall within the scope of a data protection regime (La Diega 2023, 246-8, 258f.). In fact, Regulation 2018/1807 applies in place of the GDPR when data is anonymous but when the dataset is mixed, i.e. it contains both personal and non-personal data, the GDPR applies.

Other issues not addressed here are: the correct identification of the legal grounds for each processing activity, the complex identification of data protection roles among many entities involved in this context; the granularity

² As regards the concepts of DPIA, privacy by design and the content of the GDPR, see the separate deliverable for the EMDAS Project “Digital and data sovereignty: the applicable legal frameworks and the case study of the IoT”.

of the data subjects' consents, the possible application of the e-privacy Directive and the rules on the cross border transfer of personal data (Chapter V of the GDPR). AI analytical tools applied to the energy sector raise complementary concerns. Generally speaking, such concerns are related to the recurring problems addressed by data protection regimes: how to gather and process data. At the same time, AI systems amplify those problems because of the way data is collected and used (Solove 2025, 5f.). Consider two examples in the energy sector. With regard to data collection, the training process of AI models heavily depends on the quality of data sets. There is abundant evidence that such data sets can be biased in several ways: they can refer to a limited geographical area, to limited types of social relationships, or to skewed value judgments. Such biases lead to decisions about energy and climate policies that do not contribute to mitigation and adaptation goals (Debnath et al. 2023). Article 10 AI Act aims at avoiding biases by requiring quality criteria for training, validation and testing of data sets employed with high-risk AI systems. Note, however, that the implementation of such criteria could be difficult: techniques to mitigate biases in AI systems are being developed, but they involve complex issues like the measurement of different types of biases, trade-offs between fairness and accuracy, or which groups to prioritize when unbiasing (Ferrara 2024). Furthermore, only AI systems for critical energy infrastructures qualify as high-risk (Annex III AI Act). All other AI systems deployed in the energy sector do not have mandatory quality criteria.

Even thorniest issues arise from AI data processing. AI systems generate new data from the recognition of patterns not visible to humans. This artificial or synthetic data stems from computer simulations and algorithms with the goal of replacing or augmenting costlier and difficult to access real data. Synthetic data can even be generated without collecting any real data. Already by mid-2020s, it was estimated to represent the largest portion of AI training data (Gal and Lynskey 2024). This means that protecting individual personal data and granting the right to correct and delete it is not enough. New information about individual or group behaviour can be inferred without data subjects knowing such an analytic process takes place (Solove 2025, 36-40).

Both in the EU and the USA, it is unclear whether and how data protection regimes apply to synthetic data (Gal and Lynskey 2024, 1121-43; Wiebe 2024). For the time being, Article 50(2) AI Act requires providers of AI systems generating synthetic data to ensure that the outputs of the AI system are marked in a machine-readable format and detectable as artificially generated or manipulated. While this transparency obligation may increase awareness of the impact of synthetic data, it does not restrict its use. No disclosure obligations for targeted data subject are foreseen.

In the case of energy data processing, techniques known as non-intrusive load monitoring (NILM) are deployed to disaggregate energy data and extract very detailed information about households' features. The highest inference accuracy of NILM can be obtained with machine learning solutions. It has been shown that information about each specific electric appliance, user presence in the house, financial and health conditions, as well as multimedia and TV channel watching preferences, can be identified (Schirmer & Mporas 2023). The accuracy of AI processing is further improved by the increasing availability of public datasets, private datasets used to offer commercial services for data analytics, and open source platforms allowing to share previously trained AI models (Sheikh et al. 2023; Altamimi et al. 2024). Though, the larger the number of energy datasets, the higher the risk of inferences leading to data breaches.

Predictably, the first reaction to data protection concerns was technological. Several privacy-enhancing technologies (PETs) are said to reduce risks related to data misuse. Many taxonomies of such technologies were proposed. For the purposes of this discussion, a distinction can be made between PETs that reduce and do not reduce the amount of available data. Anonymization, pseudonymization, and aggregation belong to the category of PETs that reduce the amount of available data. With regard to pseudonymization, Voyez et al. (2025) show for a large data set of French consumers that mass re-identification is possible for over 90% of consumers if a few pieces of information are known. At least in theory, anonymization should be more effective. One example is differential privacy: a controlled amount of noise is added to data in such a manner that an attacker cannot determine if an individual is (or is not) a member of a given population. Aggregate data can be shared with a low risk of de-anonymization (Teng et al. 2022, 30f.; Cardenas et al. 2023, 20-33). Solutions that allow to use data without increasing the risk of leakage rely on decentralized architectures. For example, federated learning is a machine learning method that exploits computational resources at each node

of a system to carry out data analysis. Communication requirements are reduced because raw data is kept locally and only model updates are shared with central entities or third parties (Teng et al. 2022, 40-42).

It is unlikely that data protection concerns in the energy sector (or in any sector) can only be addressed with PETs. To begin with, PETs differ along many dimensions: investment costs, parties involved, how computing resources are organized, effectiveness in reducing the risks of data breaches, and the quantity of data excluded from processing (Kua et al. 2023; El Mestari et al. 2024). This means that choices have to be made about each PET to be implemented. Who should choose and how to share the costs of PETs between companies and users is unclear.

Secondly, choices about PETs cannot be made without considering their impact on interoperability among systems. The level of data protection should be considered across the different layers of the physical and digital energy infrastructures. Thirdly, how PETs perform depends on the details of their implementation. Solutions that are assumed to work in specific cases could not work in other cases (Cardenas et al. 2023, 38). Companies negotiate the design of PETs both internally and with regulators and other stakeholders. Less costly solutions could be selected, even though the protection they grant to users is far from acceptable levels. It cannot be excluded that PETs are sometimes implemented to make overbroad claims about the effectiveness of anonymization and completely sidestep data protection regimes (Steed and Acquisti 2025). Fourthly, all PETs necessarily enshrine a specific balance between the utility of data from a commercial or systemic point of view and the protection of individual interests. What such a balance should look like needs to be openly discussed (Gal and Lynskey 2024, 1148f.).

Clearly, techno-solutionism should be discarded here. There is a need for data governance, to be understood as a regulatory framework providing clear guidance about the sharing of personal and non-personal energy data. All the digital technologies implemented in the energy sector should be included in such regulatory framework. A systemic approach is required to ensure that connections among smart technologies do not work to the detriment of users' data protection (Sovacool and Del Rio 2020, 15f.).

Data governance for the energy sector emerges from the interplay between sector-specific and horizontal data protection regimes. The EU made a major move toward a sector-specific data protection regime with Art. 20, 23 and 24 Dir. 2019/944. Although the general data protection regime was explicitly referred to, these provisions were aimed at ensuring the right of energy consumers to access their metering data and share them with third parties who offer demand response programs and other energy services.

Hence, the sector-specific provisions had to be understood as complementary to the horizontal regime of the GDPR. This relationship has been more difficult to manage than expected. To begin with, Dir. 2019/944 did not clarify the legal grounds for energy data processing. Apart from data processing justified by the consent of the consumer, no specific legal obligations were introduced to allow energy data sharing and reuse on a large scale. Member States were left the choice to introduce such obligations and specify who the parties eligible for data sharing are (Huhta 2020, 17-21).

Secondly, Dir. 2019/944 did not clarify how energy data management had to be balanced with the competing interests of data holders, data users and data subjects. As observed by Ducuing (2020), the two main goals were to avoid discriminatory use of energy data by network operators and to establish a data infrastructure for a plurality of energy services. Both of them can only be accomplished with a detailed regulation of the relationships among the different groups.

Thirdly, some provisions of Dir. 2019/944 could be interpreted not as complementary to the GDPR, but as alternative to it. This was the case for data portability, regulated in much more detail by Article 20(e) Dir. 2019/944 than in the GDPR (Graef et al. 2020; Lavrijssen et al. 2022).

The sector-specific regime for energy data was further extended by other two interventions. First, Reg. 2023/1162 introduced a reference model setting out common rules and procedures for the business, function and information layers (SGTF 2022). These layers are related to so-called information interoperability. The communication and component layers, related to technical interoperability, are left to Member States' choices.

The EU reference model does not prevent Member States from adopting divergent national practices. Still today, Member States differ significantly from the point of view of the degree of centralization or decentralization of energy data management (Beckstedde and Rossetto 2025). Though, they are required to report about the implementation of the reference model. National practices are collected in a publicly available repository to be managed by ENTSO-E and the DSO Entity. These two bodies shall also advise the Commission about future revisions to the reference model.

The new Interoperability Network for the Energy Transition was established with the goal of providing horizontal coordination and support to the European interoperability ecosystem. However gradual this approach can be, it is a big step forward to develop cross-border data exchanges and multiply the solutions for data governance. While the early interventions embraced a narrow meaning of interoperability and only focused on the technical aspects of devices, the new approach considers the systemic aspects of interoperability in all architectural layers and for all energy services (Reif & Meeus 2022).

The reference model covers both historical and real-time data. Four different roles were identified, to be performed by distinct entities or jointly by the same entity: the metered data administrator, storing and distributing data; the metering point administrator, managing metering points characteristics; the permission administrator, responsible for the register of data access permissions; the data access provider, responsible for facilitating access to data. While the first two roles are likely to be played by DSOs, other entities could play the other two roles. The four roles do not map explicitly onto the concepts of data controller and processor in the GDPR. While the metered data administrator and metering point administrator qualify as joint controllers, the permission administrator and the data access provider could qualify as joint controllers or processors. Note, however, that Reg. 2023/1162 does not introduce any new lawful ground for processing beyond the data subject's consent. Hence, these provisions only foster data sharing to the extent they harmonize procedures for cross-border data exchanges.

The second intervention extending the sector-specific regime was undertaken with the regulation of new energy data flows in the amendments to the Electricity Directive (Dir. 2024/1711, transposed in Italy with Legislative Decree no. 3/2026) and to the Electricity Regulation (Reg. 2024/1747). In order to foster energy sharing, final customers are entitled to appoint an energy sharing administrator and receive metering data from network operators (Article 15a Dir. 2019/944). Energy data can also be shared with multiple suppliers for the same connection point (Article 4 Dir. 2019/944). Moreover, dedicated measurement devices may be used for the observability and settlement of demand response and flexibility services, including from energy storage facilities (Article 7b Reg. 2019/943). These new measurement devices might be needed where smart meters are not available. The general data protection regime applies in this case as well, but Rec. 19 Reg. 2024/1747 explicitly refers to a new legal basis for the processing of legal data. Does this mean that, for the new data flows related to flexibility services, consent is not required? This is not clear, because Art. 7b(1) still refers to the consent of the final customer. Nicolai and Münchmeyer (2025) point out a lack of coordination with Reg. 2023/1162, both because it only refers to smart meters and not to dedicated measurement devices and because it always requires consent as a legal basis for data processing.

More detailed procedures for data exchange in relation to demand response programs and flexibility markets for DERs are included in the forthcoming Network Code on Demand Response (Art. 53-54 ACER 2025a), planned for adoption in 2026. The code requires national regulation or legislation to establish the conditions for using data from the dedicated measurement devices (Art. 13). It will be complemented by an implementing Regulation on interoperability requirements and non-discriminatory and transparent procedures for access to data for demand response.

In the most recent evolution of sector-specific regulation, it is difficult to discover the signs of a significant expansion of individual digital sovereignty. The GDPR provided the baseline for data protection, but uncertainty about its application to energy data was not completely dispelled. In several Member States, fears about risks of mass surveillance arising from the granularity of data collected through smart meters loom large (Baumgart and Espinosa Apráez 2024, 514-525).

The forthcoming Citizens Energy Package (EC 2025f) and the Strategic Roadmap for Digitalisation and AI in the Energy Sector (EC 2025g) promise to foster consumers' trust in innovative services and digital technologies. Though, they veer too much toward techno-solutionist approaches. Less attention is paid to the broader impact digitalization could have on consumers' lifestyle, as well as the risk that old and new inequalities about access to energy services are left unaddressed (Gantioler et al. 2023). Strengthening individual sovereignty should mean that some digital technologies are banned until the benefits they generate for all categories of consumers are proven beyond doubt. This approach clashes with the collective dimension of sovereignty, which prioritizes the systemic benefits of digitalization. In the next section, we shall see that horizontal legislation on data governance reinforces the same trend toward collective sovereignty.

6.2 The second trajectory: data governance and data infrastructures

Interactions between sector-specific and horizontal data governance became more complex with the implementation of the European strategy for data (EC 2020a). Four such interactions shall be highlighted.

To begin with, Dir. 2019/1024 requires public bodies and undertakings, as well as private undertakings operating public services, to facilitate re-use of data they control to stimulate innovation in products and services. Data about the environment and energy resources are included among the high-value datasets whose re-use shall be possible with minimal legal restrictions and free of charge (Reg. 2023/138, only for public bodies). Many benefits for energy and climate policies can be expected from the availability of these public datasets. At the same time, it was pointed out before that AI models trained on large public datasets increase the risk of de-anonymization. Furthermore, the additional risk of group profiling should be considered. Even when no personal data are involved, groups of people can become the target of manipulative strategies whose negative impact is no less worrisome than individual harms following data breaches (Mantelero 2022, 7-10; Haggart and Tusikov 2023, 245-7; Gal and Lynskey 2024, 1141-3; van der Sloot 2024, 177).

Secondly, the Data Governance Act (DGA: Reg. 2022/868) put in place a general framework aimed at building trust among public and private data holders, data subjects and data users. The provisions about data intermediation services could find significant applications in the energy sector. Data intermediaries are supposed to reduce barriers to data sharing for both personal and non-personal data. With specific regard to personal data, data intermediaries should help data subjects to exercise their rights. This measure should overcome the well-known weaknesses of consent as a lawful ground for data processing. Plenty of evidence shows that data subjects are unable to understand privacy policies. Trustworthy data intermediaries could become the single reference point data subjects need to manage their personal data in a variety of markets. In the energy sector, data intermediaries could play the roles of both permission administrator and data access provider referred to in Reg. 2023/1162. To be sure, data intermediaries could face resistance from market players whose business models are directly linked to exclusive control of energy data. This could be the case for energy companies collecting data with the purpose of supplying energy efficiency services, advertising companies collecting data with the purpose of offering products and services, or insurance companies collecting data with the purpose of knowing households' health status (Del Rio et al. 2020). The main question is whether data intermediaries will still enable all data-driven business models or foreclose those not compatible with heightened data protection.

Thirdly, the Data Act (DAct23: Reg. 2023/2854) complemented both Reg. 2018/1807 on the free flow of non-personal data and the DGA to ensure that barriers to non-personal data sharing are smoothed out. Doubts were expressed about the inclusion of smart meters within the definition of connected products in the DAct23 (Nicolai and Münchmeyer 2025). However, excluding most energy data from horizontal data governance would contradict the main thrust of the EU data strategy, clearly focused on the widest possible interoperability of all data sets. The preferable approach is to assess the interplay between the horizontal and sector-specific legislation. From this point of view, two aspects deserve to be highlighted.

First, the DAct23 grants energy customers full access to both personal and non-personal data generated by the digital equipment they use. This data access right is much broader than the portability right already granted by Art. 20 GDPR. It is also broader than the access rights included in Reg. 2023/1162, because the latter only

refers to metering and consumption data. Hence, both personal and non-personal data generated by smart meters and other smart equipment (in line with the IoT approach) shall be made available to energy customers. The latter can then share them, directly or through data intermediaries, with third parties who supply energy services. Skepticism was expressed about the effectiveness of data sharing mechanisms that depend on households' consent. Unless the new provisions succeed in fostering trust, many households might still be unwilling to share data (Eckardt and Kerber 2024, 130-2; Tombal and Graef 2024). Third parties could ask for access to non-personal data without involving households. In this case, much will depend on how bargaining unfolds between data holders (e.g. in the energy sector manufacturers of smart devices, network operators and suppliers) and data users (e.g. aggregators and energy services companies).

Second, the DAct23 excludes from sharing obligations information inferred by means of complex algorithms or more generally requiring additional investments (Rec. 15 DAct23). The goal is to protect investments in technologies that generate data. This is the same goal that justifies restrictions on data sharing when intellectual property rights and trade secrets are involved (Art. 1(8), 4(6-8), 5(9-11), 11(2), 13(5)(b), 19(3), 30(6), 43 DAct23; Tombal and Graef 2024, 212-4). However, it was pointed out before that synthetic data inferred through AI models might completely bypass data protection regimes. Moreover, data holders (usually manufacturers of IoT devices) can recover their investments through the price of the products they sell. Therefore, restrictions on data sharing might be too broad and dampen innovation (Eckardt and Kerber 2024, 124-6).

The fourth and last interaction concerns EU-based digital infrastructures. They are being developed to reduce dependence from US and Chinese suppliers. Building up an EU horizontal framework for data sharing would be of little avail if all components of the digital supply chain, from data storage to platforms to computing resources, were subject to foreign jurisdictions. Common European data spaces are the main answer. The concept was born in computer science to identify a decentralized architecture in which intra-organizational data are stored at source. It then evolved into a business concept for the collaboration on data across organizations and within an industry (Otto 2022). The European Strategy for Data (EC 2020a) turned this concept into one of the pillars of EU data governance. For data holders, the main advantage is the possibility to maintain control of data; for data users, the possibility to access a larger number of data sets. Regulatory authorities, too, can exploit data spaces to design policies and monitor compliance. The International Data Spaces Association forges an explicit link between data spaces and data sovereignty: they allow organizations, governments, and individuals to control their data, create an environment of trust and reliability, and promote interoperability among participants.

Common data spaces in fourteen domains were planned, including energy and the Green Deal (EC 2024a). Funding was provided both for projects aimed at developing data spaces in specific sectors and for the coordination of the different initiatives through the Data Spaces Support Centre. In the energy sector, EU funding was provided to the Energy Data Spaces Cluster projects for the preparatory actions leading to the Common European Energy Data Space (CEEDS) (Dognini et al. 2024). From 2025, the INSIEME project, co-funded by the Digital Europe Programme, started the deployment phase for the establishment of a federated architecture to connect existing data exchange platforms across Europe.

The governance of data spaces should significantly differ from dominant digital platforms: the former shall reflect the agreement about data sharing among participants to data spaces; the latter exploit data according to the profit-maximizing strategies of the platform operator (Schurig et al. 2024). The regulatory framework for data spaces was at least partly delineated by the DGA and the DAct23. The operator of a common data space could match the definition of data intermediaries. According to Rec. 28 DGA, data intermediaries are orchestrators of data sharing ecosystems open to all interested parties in the context of common European data spaces. Alternatively, a common data space could be managed by a governing entity and only commercial relationships between data holders and users be facilitated by data intermediaries (Dietrich & Gutiérrez David 2024). If this second option is chosen, none of the requirements for neutrality established by the DGA apply. This means that the governing entity of the common data space should be subject to strict competition law scrutiny, especially if it controls strategic cloud infrastructures.

The interplay between the investments in digital infrastructures and governance choices is even more visible in the projects on digital twins of electricity networks. Different definitions of digital twins have been proposed since the 1990s. More recently, the integration of Big Data, IoT, cloud services, and AI has allowed to develop broader virtual representations of single assets (e.g. a wind turbine) and of more complex grids. The main goal is to generate a virtual representation of the energy-relevant systems which is fully synchronized with the physical space. The bilateral exchange of data between the digital and the physical spaces can be exploited to increase the operational efficiency of energy assets and infrastructures (Thwe et al. 2025). Investments in costly grid upgrades could be significantly curtailed. Furthermore, the information provided by the digital twins can ease the reduction of GHG emissions. For example, a study carried out on the Italian energy system shows that emissions can be reduced by 7,3% compared to reference values for 2021. National energy costs can be reduced as well, in a range between 15% and 33% (The European House – Ambrosetti and Lutech 2023, 96f.).

The Commission called upon the European TSOs and DSOs to develop a digital twin of the electricity grids (EC 2022d, 7). A Joint Task Force was established by ENTSO-E and the DSO Entity to draw out proposals on the digital twin (DSO Entity and ENTSO-E 2025). Several EU-funded projects contributed in-depth knowledge about possible federated architectures and highlighted the tight connections between digital twins and common energy data spaces (TwinEU 2024; DSO4DT 2025).

The benefits expected from digital twins are heavily dependent on the resolution of complex governance issues. The real-time connection between the digital and the physical spaces assumes an unprecedented cooperation across the energy industry. Such cooperation is needed to ensure a high degree of interoperability, standardization of data formats and communication protocols, data sharing agreements and cybersecurity measures (Jørgensen and Ma 2025a). None of these requirements is within reach. Cooperation could be lacking both because network operators are not able to shoulder the investment costs of digitalization and because of the disruptive organizational changes to the management of the grids that digital twins could bring. No less relevant are the liability issues arising from the automation of management tasks: who should maintain the digital twin? Should its recommendations always be followed?

At a broader level, the very meaning of governance becomes contested. Who decides which information to include in the virtual replicas of energy infrastructures, which interests to take into account, and when to trust the virtual replicas? (Solman et al. 2022; Michalec 2025). In the EU-funded projects, the governance issues are sometimes described as barriers to be overcome in order to enable the digital twins (e.g. TwinEU 2024, 54). This is a misleading approach. Governance mechanisms are needed to manage diverging interests and select the technologies to be implemented.

Governance mechanisms are also needed to remedy a major weakness of the European policies for common data spaces and other digital infrastructures, that is their dependency on cloud services provided by the US Big Tech. Attempts at reducing their dominance have so far failed, both at national and EU level. The Gaia-X project was supposed to represent one of the backbones for the digital infrastructures supporting the common data spaces (Gaia-X 2021). The individual dimension of sovereignty was expressed both through solutions that would give individuals control of their digital identities and through the idea of a federation of data commons in which choices about individual data ownership would become possible (Adler-Nissen and Eggeling 2024, 1003-1005). However, US and Chinese companies joined it, thus showing that it could not represent a credible vehicle for EU digital sovereignty (Obendiek and Siedl 2023, 1318-22). Whether other EU projects will be more successful in creating alternatives to US and Chinese cloud services is unclear (Bria et al. 2025, 65-71). One possible scenario is the repurpose of the Gaia-X project toward the development of EU standards for cloud services. Even though non-EU companies control the digital infrastructures, EU sovereignty would be protected by requiring those companies to comply with standards that take EU's and Member States' interests into account (Baur 2025).

Note, however, that a proposal for an EU Cloud Services Scheme, modelled after the French certification scheme and with strong sovereignty restrictions, was already advanced in 2020. If approved according to the CSA procedures (sec. 4.1), the scheme would have led to a harmonized regulatory framework for cloud

services. Several Member States rejected the sovereignty restrictions, which would have prevented agreements on the supply of digital services with US companies. Moreover, sovereignty restrictions entail political choices that cannot be made with an implementing act (Eckhardt and Hoffmann 2025). Further attempts were made to overcome the political disagreement with the scheme. Most sovereignty restrictions were removed, and Member States were allowed to decide which ones they were interested in introducing (Rone 2024; Calcara 2025). Even with this compromise solution, by mid-2025 the scheme had not been enacted.

Should sovereignty restrictions on cloud services be introduced with EU legislation, they would have to comply with the subsidiarity and proportionality principles, avoid infringing Art. 16 of the EU Charter on Fundamental Rights on entrepreneurial freedom, and be designed to be compatible with the WTO obligations on international trade in services (Eckhardt and Hoffmann 2025, 21-32). Note, however, that both Art. 48 GDPR and Art. 32 DAct23 already prevent providers of digital services from transferring personal and non-personal data to third countries in case of conflict (or not adequacy) with EU or national law or outside of international agreements (Eckhardt and Hoffmann 2025, 23f.). These provisions, too, need to be assessed from the point of view of their compatibility with fundamental rights and WTO principles.

Just introducing stronger data localization requirements does not address the conflict of laws with the USA or other jurisdictions, nor do the requirements contribute to enhance cybersecurity (Christakis 2024; Michels et al. 2025). At the same time, it could be argued that security concerns are already addressed by these provisions and further legislative initiatives are not needed. The Commission adopted the opposite stance by starting a consultation for a proposed Cloud and AI Development Act (EC 2025c). One of the goals of this initiative is to “(e)nsure that a set of narrowly defined highly critical use cases can be operated using highly secure EU-based cloud capacity, while creating the conditions for the EU cloud industry to develop secure processing capabilities to serve the needs of these highly critical use cases”. In a similar vein, the announced European Data Union Strategy (EC 2025d, e) is expected to include an international data strategy with actions to safeguard the export of EU data, access to common European data spaces and priority engagement on bilateral and multilateral levels as well as development of international rules conducive to data sharing on a contractual basis.

In practice, most Member States already rely on US companies for the digital services they need. Therefore, a more plausible scenario is that the EU strategy fails to create an EU digital infrastructure but allows Member States to develop their own industrial policies and negotiate better deals with the US companies (Calcara 2025). The latter adapt their offer to European sovereignty concerns by implementing technological solutions, including data residency and cryptographic solutions, that promise to safeguard the confidentiality of European customers’ data. However, technological solutions cannot ensure full control on data flows and contribute to strengthening the dominance of US companies (Blancato and Carr 2024). Moreover, Western Europe Member States could be better positioned to negotiate with US companies than Eastern Europe Member States (Rone 2025). This observation again puts center stage the disagreement about the meanings of digital sovereignty.

Much the same pattern can be observed in Italy with cloud services for the public administration. Funding from the Recovery and Resilience Plan was used to establish the Strategic National Pole (PSN), a new company in charge of transferring most public data to data servers located on the national territory. The identification of the concession holder for the PSN was highly contentious (Magli 2024). A consortium of two digital companies (Fastweb, controlled by Swisscom, and Aruba, an Italian company) won the tender with a better offer. However, thanks to a right of first refusal, the concession was granted to another consortium led by TIM (with a minority share of the Italian government) and including Cassa Depositi e Prestiti (controlled by the Italian government), Leonardo (controlled by the Italian government) and Sogei (a public company). Administrative judges later found that the TIM consortium had not complied with the requirements of the tender, but the winning consortium was only entitled to damages (Council of State no. 9210/23, with comment by Lorenzoni 2024). The criteria to quantify the lost profits for the Fastweb/Aruba consortium were identified, but the exact amount of the damage remains to be determined through the negotiation between the parties, or alternatively by the administrative judge should they fail to reach an agreement (Regional Administrative Tribunal of Lazio no. 196/24; Council of State no. 4134/25). Even though the administrative judges limited damages to 35% of lost profits, the total amount could still be in the hundreds of millions of Euros. In the meanwhile, the PSN

started its operations. Italian public administrations are offered the possibility to enter into contracts with the PSN for the cloud services they need. Such services are mainly supplied by AWS, Microsoft, Google and Oracle (Blotta 2023, 2024; PSN 2025). This means that the PSN acts as an intermediary between the dominant US companies and the public administrations. Moreover, data of strategic relevance are stored in the servers located on the national territory. Public administrations can also independently procure cloud services from other suppliers certified by the ACN. However, the Italian cloud strategy is not conducive to the reduction of the market power of dominant non-EU companies.

The developments of EU data governance can be critically assessed from the point of view of the collective and individual dimensions of digital sovereignty.

With regard to the former, the common data spaces should foster innovation in the digital realm. But if they are built on the digital resources made available by the Big Tech, will they really strengthen EU digital sovereignty? It could be argued that the attempt to develop a data governance system alternative to the US and Chinese ones sows the seeds for EU leadership in next-generation technologies, from edge cloud computing to 6G to quantum, photonics and neuromorphic technologies for communication and processing (Bria et al. 2025).

But does it mean that, in order to foster its digital sovereignty, EU data governance will be strictly guarded, with restrictions on data access for non-EU parties? For example, should Big Tech be prevented from using the common European data spaces to train their AI systems? Should broader data localization policies be introduced? As mentioned above, it is doubtful that such restrictions comply with international obligations. They can also be detrimental to EU interests if they prevent EU companies from accessing non-EU digital technologies.

Cybersecurity might be degraded if less advanced solutions are adopted. More generally, sovereignty restrictions are likely to fail when supply chains are tightly interconnected. If several segments of the chain are located outside the EU, it is unlikely that all data flows along the chain will be regulated according to the EU regulatory framework (see, with regard to the semiconductors supply chains, Carrapico and Farrand 2025).

Furthermore, taking the lead on next-generation technologies could be difficult if their development depends on other technologies, previous investments and scientific collaborations. Innovation processes are often path dependent, thus creating uncertainty about the success of early technological choices (see with regard to quantum technologies Gercek and Seskir 2025). The digital twins are another case in point: their development is largely due to foundational technologies like industrial IoT, cloud and edge computing, blockchain, and AI/machine learning (Maillard et al. 2025). The three largest markets will all make their bets, of course, but approaches dominated by sovereignty concerns do not increase the chances of ending up with the dominant technologies.

As far as the individual dimension of sovereignty is concerned, the viability of the data intermediaries' model is the key factor. Doubts were expressed about the possibility that a neutral data intermediary could really compete with tech giants facing none of the restrictions imposed by the DGA (Carovano and Finck 2023, 11f.). However, it must be acknowledged that the approach exclusively based on the individual right to data protection and the consent of the data subject has already failed. Data intermediaries turn the individual approach into a collective approach. In the energy sector, they could succeed in breaking up the energy companies' monopoly on energy data and increasing opportunities for data sharing. To some extent, such a development would foster the convergence of the collective and the individual dimensions. Of course, the risk that energy consumers will receive limited benefits from the digitalization of the energy sector cannot be excluded at this stage. As pointed out by Ryan et al. (2024), in common data spaces a delicate equilibrium has to be sought between the sovereignty of individuals, organizations and states. No such equilibrium is possible if only one dimension of sovereignty is considered.

7. Policy

The analysis in the previous sections shows that the concept of digital sovereignty significantly contributes to orient EU and national regulatory choices. There are, however, two open issues. The first one is that the regulatory measures aimed at fostering the collective dimension of sovereignty might prove ineffective, or less effective than hoped for. The second issue is that, when it clashes with the collective dimension, individual sovereignty is rarely prioritized. We advance four policy recommendations that could help re-design EU and national policies for the twin transition in the coming years.

To begin with, a joint assessment of the collective and individual dimensions of digital sovereignty should always be required. Only measures that address both dimensions should be deemed acceptable. Such an assessment should be carried out at both EU and Member States levels, *ex-ante* and *ex-post*. Compared to the current situation, the joint assessment would have two advantages: first, it would increase transparency on the justifications for interventions that could have protectionist goals or reduce cooperation at international level; second, it would reduce the set of measures that can be justified by sovereignty concerns. From a normative point of view, those measures entail too many negative collateral effects and should be used sparingly. With this joint assessment, several gaps in the current regulatory frameworks should be filled. For example, the distribution of cybersecurity costs among suppliers of digital services, industrial users and non-industrial users could be made more visible. Liability issues for cyber harms should be clarified. Individuals should be given better decision-making tools to make meaningful choices about security and data processing.

The second policy recommendation has to do with the prioritization of climate goals. The analysis in the previous sections shows that only in a few cases the EU and Italian legislation explicitly aim at fostering the synergies of the twin transition. Environmental sustainability of digital technologies is poised to become one of the aspects of the tech race between the USA and China. American innovations were not designed to comply with climate targets. Conversely, China entered the tech race with the goal of promoting sustainable innovations. The launch of DeepSeek, a large language model that claims to reduce the environmental impacts of AI systems, exemplifies this strategy (Rivero-Silva et al. 2025). If environmental sustainability becomes a decisive geopolitical factor, there seems to be ample room for the EU regulatory framework to shape the direction of digital innovations. The hierarchy of priorities should be turned upside down: instead of prioritizing any kind of digital innovation, no matter how sustainable it is, all EU resources should be channelled toward innovations that really contribute to the low-carbon transition. Thanks to the European Green Deal and the climate neutrality target by 2050, the EU is better positioned than its competitors to support the diffusion of sustainability standards. The implications of such strategy could be dramatic: some US and Chinese technologies could be excluded from the Internal Market because they cannot comply with the EU sustainability requirements. At the same time, raising the bar of environmental sustainability would avoid accusations of economic protectionism. Of course, environmental standards for digital technologies should also be designed with the goal of supporting the low-carbon transition in developing countries. From this point of view, a shared understanding of digital sovereignty entirely focused on sustainability should be easier to achieve. These advantages should be underlined to contrast the opposite narrative brought forward by some parts of the industry, which identifies sustainability obligations as the main culprit of the slow pace of technological innovation in the EU.

The third policy recommendation refers to the identification of incentive-compatible solutions to address sovereignty concerns along supply chains. Requirements about cybersecurity and data processing in the EU legislation are demanding and shall be implemented along the chains. However, it is not clear how this extra-territorial effect of EU legislation could become effective if those chains are largely dominated by non-EU companies. In public procurement procedures, tendering authorities could be able to impose the EU requirements. But for private EU companies who deal with non-EU suppliers, the negotiation could be much more asymmetric. Risks cannot be reduced by simply reducing dependencies. In many cases, no alternatives are available (for semiconductors see Carrapico and Farrand 2025; for renewable energy technologies see Guadagno and Stehrer 2025). After all, supply chains are organized exactly because interdependencies are expected to provide benefits. Therefore, the goal should be to strengthen the bargaining power of EU companies in the relationship with non-EU suppliers. Instead of just introducing mandatory requirements, an

additional strategy should be to organize collective purchasing platforms at EU level. They should ensure that negotiation takes place on equal footing and be able to verify compliance with EU requirements. This is very much the same strategy the EU implemented to deal with its dependency from external gas suppliers (Frontier Economics 2024) and from external suppliers of critical raw materials (Amighini et al. 2023; Tröster et al. 2025). Reference to collective bargaining for cybersecurity requirements in supply chains can also be found in guidance from ENISA (2025b, 68). At national level, electricity distribution systems operators in France and the Netherlands are already engaged in joint procurement initiatives (DSO Entity and E.DSO 2025a). This proposal could face opposition from Member States who prefer to engage in bilateral deals on digital services with non-EU suppliers. Though, the high risks from current digital dependencies and the complexity of the supply chains involved suggest that the gradual and voluntary implementation of EU-level collective bargaining could be a more promising route than the replacement of foreign technologies with EU ones.

The fourth policy recommendation concerns the energy sector. The increasing density of both the horizontal and sector-specific regulatory regimes can be expected to also increase the complexity of the interplay in the coming years. The concept of digital sovereignty should be exploited to reduce the frictions among the different agents (states, organizations, and individuals) advancing conflicting claims in energy markets. Those frictions are mostly related to the transformations prompted by the twin transition. In the cybersecurity domain, the main problem is that the ongoing decentralization of energy systems makes it more difficult to ensure the required investments. In the data protection domain, too little is still known about the advantages that data sharing could bring to energy consumers.

To address these shortcomings, in both horizontal and sector-specific regulatory regimes, specific evaluation procedures should be put in place to assess the impacts of clean technologies and provide balanced solutions to conflicting sovereignty claims. Instead of just considering the costs and benefits of those technologies, the evaluation procedures should delve with a larger array of factors enabling and hampering the digital sovereignty of each agent. The model for such procedures could be represented by technology assessments, a well-known set of socio-epistemic practices helping to shape innovation policies (Hennen et al. 2023; Grunwald 2024)

With regard to cybersecurity, the evaluation procedures should match obligations to the role each energy player plays. The size of those players does matter, but it cannot be the only factor.

With regard to data protection, the evaluation procedures should clarify to what extent the benefits of data sharing for the energy system as a whole are compatible with an enlargement of the autonomy of individual energy consumers.

These transparency-enhancing purposes could represent a real turning point. Up to now, the concept of digital sovereignty has been deemed useful mainly thanks to its uncertain meaning. What is proposed here is to move in the opposite direction and openly discuss the consequences of regulatory choices inspired by sovereignty concerns for the twin transition.

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